

ESREIN
Economic and Social
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Journal of Economics, Law & Society

Advancing Ethical and Socially
Responsible Finance

Vol. 1 - No. 1 - June - 2024

Published by:

Economic and Social Research Institute

Blagovac 192,

71320 Vogošća

Bosnia and Herzegovina

<https://jels.esrein.org>

jels@esrein.org

ISSN (Online): 3029-3189

JELS

JOURNAL OF ECONOMICS, LAW & SOCIETY

Advancing Ethical and Socially Responsible Finance

Volume 1 | Number 1 | June 2024

Published by

ESREIN
Economic and Social
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JOURNAL OF ECONOMICS, LAW AND SOCIETY

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ABOUT THE JOURNAL

The Journal of Economics, Law, and Society (JELS) is a pioneering academic platform dedicated to the comprehensive exploration of economics, law, and society, with a distinct focus on Islamic economics, banking, and finance. Our mission is to foster interdisciplinary dialogue, cultivate a deep understanding of these interconnected disciplines, and promote the exchange of innovative research to advance both theoretical knowledge and practical applications.

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ISSN

ISSN (Online): 3029-3189

Published by:

Economic and Social Research Institute (ESREIN)
Blagovac 192,
71320 Vogošća
Bosnia and Herzegovina

Design & Layout by

Dr. Edib Smolo

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Editorial

Inaugural Issue of the Journal of Economics, Law, and Society (JELS)

It is with great pleasure that we present the first issue of the *Journal of Economics, Law and Society (JELS)*, a peer-reviewed journal which aims to foster academic discourse on the interconnections between economics, law, and society. It is with great expectations and enthusiasm that we begin this journal from Bosnia and Herzegovina (BiH) and confident that this journal will be of immense benefits to the academia especially in the newly emerging area of Islamic finance.

The formation of JELS is more so due to the realization of the importance of the multidisciplinary approach to solving tasks that require synthesis and integration of theory and practice across disciplines. In the modern integrated global environment, the interactions between economic processes, legal regulation and social phenomena become even more significant. Our goal is to encourage high-quality scholarship, critical thinking, and meaningful discourse on these critical issues while promoting academic study and intellectual exchange.

JELS aims at ensuring quick dissemination of research findings between researchers, universities, as well as other academic institutions across the world. Our journal will focus on the advancement that is current within various fields of study like business and management law, public administration, sociology/anthropology, economics, social work/social policy, history, education/teaching, psychology, political science/government, ethics/moral philosophy, and many others. Thus, we intend to have a broad focus in order to provide readers with the theoretical and empirical materials of an interdisciplinary nature that integrate legal and economic approaches.

All manuscripts sent to JELS are subject to rigorous double-blind review to ensure that publications in our journal reflect the highest standards of scholarship. Recently we have been focusing on new and developing topics, Islamic finance in particular, based on our conviction that more innovative solutions to the problems of financial intermediation should be sought.

The editorial board for JELS consists of distinguished academics and practitioners from various fields of law and economics. Thanks to their experience and commitment, authors will receive constructive feedback to improve their work while the review process remains effective and fast. That is why we are pleased to present to readers the rich variety of materials reflecting law and economics thinking with representatives from different countries.

As we enter this new course of action, it is our intention to become increasingly well-known on

the international level. Turning to the focus and scope of JELS, this journal sets out to solicit papers that are originated from and discuss various legal systems and theoretical inter-cultural topics. We will continue to encourage submissions of articles that contribute to improved methods in the vast area of Islamic economics, Islamic business and management, Islamic finance, and Islamic banking studies. It is also important to note that our target audience mainly consists of academicians, college teachers, postgraduate students, and other practitioners, ensuring that our journal serves as a valuable resource for those engaged in the field.

JELS has the support of the *Economic and Social Research Institute (ESREIN)*, and it is our intention to make this journal one of the leading academic journals not only in BiH but also throughout the world. In the future, we will try our best to ensure JELS will be included in top databases that could help to improve its visibility and significance among the academia.

We encourage you to join us in the exploration of the actual link which exists between economics, law and society through the first issue of the *Journal of Economics, Law and Society (JELS)*. We hope to continue receiving your stimulating inputs and to help build up the academic community via this journal. Thank you for being part of this journey and indeed, we do hope that you will be both informed and inspired by the research and information contained in these pages.

Continuing the strong focus on economic development, this inaugural issue features a variety of insightful studies. Smolo's analysis challenges conventional wisdom by demonstrating a complex relationship between finance, institutions, and economic growth (pp. 5-22). His findings suggest the need for nuanced approaches based on specific contexts.

Shifting the focus to consumer behavior, Knezović et al. explore green purchase intentions in the Middle East (pp. 23-38). Their research finds that factors like age, gender, and education have minimal impact, while geographic location holds some influence. This research highlights the need to explore green consumer behavior in the region further.

Mešković et al. delve into the under-utilized potential of Islamic investment deposits in Bosnia and Herzegovina (pp. 39-53). Their study reveals a significant knowledge gap among depositors, hindering wider adoption. The authors emphasize the need for education and awareness campaigns to unlock the potential of these deposits for financial inclusion.

The growing importance of sustainable finance is explored by Ibrić et al. who analyze the global green bond market (pp. 55-71). Their research highlights Europe's leadership in issuance, with Bosnia and Herzegovina making its debut in 2023. The study underscores the need to address limitations like inadequate infrastructure to enable further development of the green bond market in the region.

Rounding out the issue, Metadger et al. investigate the role of sukuk, a Shari'ah-compliant financial instrument, in portfolio diversification (pp. 73-89). Their study, focusing on the Dubai market, reveals a dynamic relationship between sukuk and conventional stock market, but concludes that sukuk may not function as a traditional safe-haven asset.

Our journal's inaugural issue presents a rich research tapestry, offering valuable insights for academics, policymakers, and practitioners alike. We look forward to continuing this exploration of critical themes in future issues.

Finally, we express our profound thanks to all the authors, reviewers, and other members of the editorial board for their significant contributions that has led to the production of this first issue. It is my pleasure to extend my sincere appreciation to you for your impressive and tremendous efforts

that created such a solid basis for JELS and paving the way for the coming issues loaded with remarkable research papers and remarkable dialogue. We eagerly anticipate starting the new journey and genuinely appreciate your support and input as we aim to develop JELS into an influential journal in the areas of economics, law, and society. Greetings to everyone visiting JELS, where advancing interdisciplinary research frontiers is our mission.

Edib Smolo

Editor-in-Chief

Journal of Economics, Law & Society (JELS)

The Institutions-Finance-Growth Nexus: The Case Study of EU and European Transition Economies

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ABSTRACT

This paper empirically investigates the impact of finance and institutions on economic growth using a panel data analysis covering the 2002-2019 period and focusing on three country groups: European Union (EU) member countries, European transition economies, and the overall sample taking all countries together. In contrast to the prevailing view that suggests a positive impact of finance on growth, our findings indicate that finance either decreases growth or is insignificant without evidence of non-linearity. Another finding that comes as a surprise is that institutions play no role in growth either directly or indirectly via finance in all our samples. Our findings, however, support the claim that the finance-growth nexus depends on financial development proxies and the financial and institutional development levels within sample countries.

ARTICLE HISTORY

Received: April 30, 2024

Accepted: May 07, 2024

Published: June 30, 2024

KEYWORDS

financial development; institutional development; economic growth; developed countries; transition economies; European Union

JEL CODES

C33; D02; F43; O1; O4;

HOW TO CITE

Smolo, E. (2024). The Institutions-Finance-Growth Nexus: The Case Study of EU and European Transition Economies. *Journal of Economics, Law and Society*, 1(1), 5-22. <https://doi.org/10.70009/jels.2024.1.1.1>

1. INTRODUCTION

The debate about what causes economic growth under different economic conditions is ongoing and is about to continue. The current and prevailing economic system is capitalism, which promotes an open economy with free capital and labor flows. Consequently, the authors started investigating reasons, factors, and patterns why some countries tend to develop faster than others. In short, studies show that several factors affect economic growth, such as the level, depth, and strength of financial sector development, government spending, monetary and fiscal stability, human capital, institutional development, a type of political system, and its stability – among others. Furthermore, some of these factors have positive and some negative effects on economic growth depending on the sample countries and the period under investigation.

Financial development is one of the most influential factors that affect economic growth. This debate with Schumpeter (1912) led to an extensive debate, resulting in several views. As this relationship is becoming more complex due to overall development, other factors are entering into this relationship. One of those factors is institutional development, which attracts considerable attention among researchers. Political stability, property rights, rule of law, accounting standards, control of corruption, and government efficiency are integral parts of institutional development that play a role in the finance-growth nexus (Anayiotos & Toroyan, 2009; Gani & Ngassam, 2008; Law & Habibullah, 2009; Hakimi & Hamdi, 2017; Slesman et al., 2019). Still, depending on the underlying

conditions of a particular state, this variable may affect economic growth differently. However, the overall effect of it is expected to be positive.

The entire sample comprises 38 European countries, while the other two subsamples cover 28 European Union (EU) member countries and 10 European TE countries. The existing literature, however, primarily focuses on developed economies, ignoring less developed ones, particularly transition economies (TE). These countries differ in many dimensions and are going through social, political, economic, and institutional changes that affect their overall performance. In short, TE is in dire need of institutions (financial and otherwise) that would support and promote economic growth. To address the literature gap, this study aims to address the finance-growth nexus using samples with different financial and institutional developments. The main objective of this study is to determine the effect of financial and institutional development on economic growth within the samples mentioned above. In particular, based on existing literature and unresolved issues, this study will test a few hypotheses, namely:

- H1. Financial development affects economic growth positively.
- H2. The impact of financial development on economic growth is non-linear.
- H3. The effect of financial development on economic growth depends on institutions.
- H4. The finance-growth nexus depends on proxies used for financial development indicators.
- H5. The finance-growth nexus differs in countries with different financial and institutional development.

To investigate our main objective and test the above hypotheses, the study relies on the bias-corrected least square dummy variable estimator (LSDVC) developed by Kiviet (1995). Previous studies relied on many estimation techniques. However, compared to those, LSDVC is considered superior and provides more reliable results. The study uses GDP per capita and GDP growth as dependent economic growth variables that are in line with the literature. As for the main independent variables, the study relies on traditional financial development indicators such as liquid liabilities, private credit to GDP ratios, financial institutions, and financial markets – proxies developed by Svirydzenka (2016). Institutional development is measured by two indices, one produced by the Heritage Foundation and the other by the World Governance Indicators (WGI) of the World Bank database (Kaufmann et al., 2010).

The most exciting finding was that finance decreases growth or is insignificant without evidence of non-linearity. Another important finding was that institutions play no role in direct or indirect growth via finance in all our samples. Hence, we find no support for our hypotheses H_1 , H_2 , and H_3 . However, our findings further support the idea of several authors who found that the finance-growth nexus depends on the proxies used for financial development and the level of financial and institutional development within sample countries (H_4 and H_5).

The rest of the study is structured as follows: *Section 2* provides a literature review; *Section 3* describes the data and methodology used; *Section 4* analyses empirical results; and *Section 5* provides concluding observations.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The debate on the finance-growth nexus is still ongoing. Numerous papers provided theoretical foundations (Schumpeter, 1912; Robinson, 1952; Goldsmith, 1969; Shaw, 1973; Lucas, 1988), leading to extensive empirical literature confirming and challenging those theories. As a result of these studies, several relationships have been detected over the years, and four significant views have surfaced. The most prevailing view is the ‘supply-leading hypothesis,’ where finance leads to economic

growth (Beck et al., 2000; Levine et al., 2000; Christopoulos & Tsionas, 2004; Seetanah et al., 2009; Bittencourt, 2012; Beck et al., 2014). The second view is the ‘demand-following hypothesis,’ where growth precedes financial development (Favara, 2003; Naceur & Ghazouani, 2007; Hsueh et al., 2013; Bezemer et al., 2014; Samargandi et al., 2015; Carré & L’œillet, 2018). The ‘feedback hypothesis’ or a bi-directional relationship is the third view in the literature where finance and growth contribute positively to each other’s development (P. O. Demetriades & Hussein, 1996; Greenwood & Smith, 1997; Cheng, 2012; Marques et al., 2013). Finally, the fourth view is the ‘neutrality hypothesis’ or no relationship between finance and growth (Lucas, 1988; Shan & Morris, 2002; Nyasha & Odhiambo, 2015).

Be it as it may, all these views are under scientific scrutiny as some studies concluded that these relationships depend on financial development proxies, methodologies, and sample countries and periods used for investigation (Fernandez & Galetovic, 1994; De Gregorio & Guidotti, 1995; Luintel & Khan, 1999; Ram, 1999; Naceur & Ghazouani, 2007; Favara, 2003; Hsueh et al., 2013; Carré & L’œillet, 2018; Nyasha & Odhiambo, 2018; Smolo, 2020b, 2021, 2022). Halkos and Trigoni (2010), Hassan et al. (2011), Hsueh et al. (2013), Marques et al. (2013), and Smolo (2020a) found more than one relationship in their studies to make things even more complicated.

Furthermore, investigating the finance-growth nexus in 24 advanced economies, Swamy and Dharani (2019) found a non-linear, inverted U-shaped relationship. In other words, a positive contribution of financial development to economic growth has its limit, and once that limit is reached, its contribution becomes negative. Law and Singh (2014), Prochniak and Wasiak (2017), and Smolo (2023) have reported similar findings.

Nevertheless, recent studies point out other factors directly and indirectly affecting this nexus. For instance, a tripartite relationship, institutions-finance-growth, attracts increasing attention from researchers. In particular, several studies highlighted the significance of institutional quality/development, such as political stability, property rights, rule of law, accounting standards, control of corruption, and government efficiency – among others – as essential ingredients in the finance-growth nexus (Anayiotos & Toroyan, 2009; P. Demetriades & Fielding, 2012; Gani & Ngassam, 2008; La Porta et al., 1998; Girma & Shortland, 2007; Law & Azman-Saini, 2008; Law & Habibullah, 2009; Hakimi & Hamdi, 2017; Slesman et al., 2019; Minović et al., 2021). For finance to affect growth positively, the institutional quality needs to reach a certain threshold. Otherwise, its impact on growth would be negative (Minea & Villieu, 2010; Djeri et al., 2020; Slesman et al., 2019).

In short, institutional quality affects economic growth directly and indirectly through its impact on financial development. Financial development may not contribute to the economic growth of Middle East and North African (MENA) countries unless institutional development is considered (Kutan et al., 2017). Efficient government and democracy contribute to efficient institutions that ultimately contribute to economic growth in Pakistan (Murtaza & Faridi, 2016). Furthermore, efficient institutions affect the economic growth of sub-Saharan African countries directly and indirectly through public debt (Sani et al., 2019). Similarly, Urbano et al. (2019) found that institutions lead to economic growth through entrepreneurship. However, besides improving the overall quality of institutions within a country, for economic growth to take place, it is equally important to reduce all sorts of inequality (Karla & Stiglitz, 2003; Nigar, 2015).

In brief, this ongoing debate on the finance-growth nexus offers inconclusive and sometimes conflicting results. This relationship is further complicated by several other factors that directly and indirectly affect economic growth through their impact on financial development. Institutional quality is the most significant factor that impacts this relationship, as represented by several indicators highlighted briefly above. While there has been much research on the finance growth nexus and developed economies, very few studies have investigated the relationship between institutions and

finance growth, especially in transition economies. Given these unresolved issues, this study sheds additional light on the institutions-finance-growth nexus, focusing on a few European samples with different financial, economic, and institutional foundations. The results are expected to offer valuable insights to policymakers and contribute to the existing literature on the topic.

3. DATA, MODEL AND METHODOLOGY

3.1. Data and Sample Selection

To investigate the relationship between financial and institutional development on one side and economic growth on the other, this study uses annual-level data for 38 countries from Europe as the primary sample. In addition, as the literature shows that impacts of finance and institutions may have different implications for economic growth due to various economic, financial, and institutional development, the primary sample is divided into two different country groups with the similar yet different financial, institutional, and economic environment: (i) EU member states (28 countries)¹ – the EU represents a trade union with a free flow of labor and capital with no tariffs or trade barriers; and (ii) European transition economies (10 countries)² – these economies are relatively small developing, and going through a transition from planned- to market-based economies.

In line with the existing literature, our dependent variable is the real per capita GDP growth rate (GDP) as a measure of economic growth (Kutan et al., 2017; Swamy & Dharani, 2019). For robustness tests, we are using GDP growth (GDPG) instead (Swamy & Dharani, 2019). Previous studies have used several proxies to analyze financial development variables. Some studies use a credit ratio to the private sector as a percentage of GDP (PR) to capture the efficiency of funds channeling to the private sector (Al-Malkawi & Abdullah, January 3; Levine, 1997; Smolo, 2020a). In contrast, others use a ratio of liquid liabilities to GDP (LL) to capture the financial sector size and depth (King & Levine, 1993; Levine, 1997; Compton & Giedeman, 2011; Law & Singh, 2014; Smolo, 2020a). However, Svirydzenka (2016) argues that these traditional variables do not reflect the multifaceted nature of financial development.

Consequently, apart from the two proxies for financial development mentioned above, this study employs two different indices suggested by Svirydzenka (2016), namely, the financial institutions index (FI) and the financial markets index (FM), with each one taking into consideration the depth, accessibility, and efficiency of financial institutions and markets. It is believed that these indices represent financial development in a more comprehensive form, providing a better picture and understanding of the role of financial development in economic growth. Furthermore, as several studies find a nonlinear relationship between finance and growth, this study uses squared terms of these financial variables (Rousseau & Wachtel, 2011; Breitenlechner et al., 2015; Haini, 2020).

Similarly, institutional development is also regarded as a complex, multidimensional concept as scholars used various indicators as its proxies. This study relies on two different measures. The first is the institutional development (overall score) the Heritage Foundation provides. The second one is the institutional quality index constructed based on six indicators from the World Governance Indicators (WGI) of the World Bank database. These indicators are control of corruption, political stability, rule of law, regulatory quality, voice and accountability, and government effectiveness developed by Kaufmann et al. (2010). However, instead of examining each indicator separately or

¹ EU member states are: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Republic of Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden and the United Kingdom. We include the United Kingdom as it was part of EU during the study period.

² European transition economies are: Albania, Armenia, Belarus, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Georgia, Moldova, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Serbia, and Ukraine.

jointly, we construct the institutional quality index using the principal component analysis (PCA). Using each indicator separately may not provide the overall quality of institutions as it is a complex phenomenon. At the same time, using all these indicators simultaneously may not be appropriate as they are highly correlated (Globerman & Shapiro, 2002; Buchanan et al., 2012). Hence, using factor analysis and following Globerman and Shapiro (2002) and Buchanan et al. (2012), we construct the institutional quality index by extracting the first principal component of those six institutional quality indicators. In addition, the study employs interaction terms of each financial development indicator with institutional development proxies to determine institutions' indirect impact on growth through financial development (Haini, 2020).

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics: all countries

Variable	Sign	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
GDP per capita growth (annual %)	GDP	684	2.84	0.33	-0.48	3.66
GDP growth (annual %)	GDPG	684	2.84	0.38	-1.82	3.69
Financial institutions	FI	648	-0.56	0.37	-1.93	-0.06
Financial markets	FM	648	-1.87	1.79	-7.79	-0.06
Liquid liabilities to GDP (%)	LL	683	4.17	0.69	2.38	6.84
Private credit to GDP (%)	PC	673	4.04	0.69	1.72	5.36
Institutional development (overall score)	ID	684	4.18	0.13	3.62	4.41
Institutional quality index	IQ	684	0.73	0.42	-0.57	1.36
Trade openness (% of GDP)	TO	684	4.63	0.42	3.82	6.01
Gross capital formation (% of GDP)	GCF	684	3.14	0.22	2.32	3.87
Government final consumption (% of GDP)	EXP	684	2.92	0.20	2.09	3.40
School enrollment, primary (% gross)	HC	662	4.62	0.05	4.44	4.87
Inflation - GDP deflator (annual %)	INF	684	2.57	0.32	-1.30	4.45

Note: All variables are in log form.

Table 2: Correlation matrix: all countries

Variables	GDP	GDPG	FI	FM	LL	PC	ID	IQ	TO	GCF	EXP	HC	INF
GDP	1.000												
GDPG	0.968	1.000											
FI	-0.258	-0.137	1.000										
FM	-0.214	-0.099	0.775	1.000									
LL	-0.211	-0.086	0.754	0.599	1.000								
PC	-0.358	-0.243	0.880	0.750	0.657	1.000							
ID	-0.078	-0.011	0.554	0.389	0.473	0.511	1.000						
IQ	-0.141	-0.032	0.780	0.761	0.599	0.736	0.722	1.000					
TO	0.083	0.107	0.064	-0.050	0.373	0.003	0.240	0.153	1.000				
GCF	0.310	0.272	-0.396	-0.401	-0.407	-0.462	-0.098	-0.254	0.056	1.000			
EXP	-0.259	-0.197	0.508	0.612	0.250	0.573	0.124	0.568	-0.029	-0.361	1.000		
HC	-0.077	-0.041	0.171	0.258	0.104	0.265	0.118	0.272	-0.091	-0.011	0.202	1.000	
INF	0.322	0.301	-0.490	-0.388	-0.399	-0.444	-0.482	-0.439	0.023	0.374	-0.203	-0.071	1.000

Note: GDP - GDP per capita growth, GDPG - GDP growth, FI - financial institutions, FM - financial markets, LL - liquid liabilities, PC - private credit, ID - institutional development, IQ - institutional quality index, GCF - gross capital formation, EXP - government consumption expenditure, TO - trade openness, HC - human capital, INF - inflation. All variables are in log form.

Furthermore, besides finance and institutions, other factors also influence economic growth. Thus, the study uses several control variables commonly used in the literature on the topic. These control variables are: GCF, the gross capital formation (% GDP) reflecting the overall economic

development of a country; TO, trade openness is measured by the sum of exports and imports of goods and services (% GDP) representing the significance of international trade on economic activities; EXP, government consumption expenditure (% GDP) as proxy for investment in physical capital; HC, measured by primary school enrolment (% Gross) and represent the human capital development; and INF, inflation rate measured by GDP deflator (annual %) indicating macroeconomic and business environment (in)stability (Beck et al., 2014; Bist, 2018; Ibrahim et al., 2017; Sabir et al., 2019; Swamy & Dharani, 2019). **Table 1** provides summary statistics of all variables used in model estimations, while **Table 2** provides the correlation matrix between these variables.

All data are sourced from World Development Indicators (World Bank), World Governance Indicators (World Bank), the Heritage Foundation, and the IMF Financial Development Index Database (Svirydzenka, 2016), covering the 2002-2019 period. The study focuses on this period for several reasons: (i) in 2002, the EURO was introduced³ and 19 EU member states are also members of the European Monetary Union, offering additional layers of financial and institutional qualities; (ii) some TE, in particular the Western Balkan countries, went through turbulent times during the '90s and it took them some years to get their economies back on track. Both these reasons may affect relationships that are the focus of this study.

3.2. Models and Methods Used

The literature is overwhelmed with numerous techniques, diverse indicators, and various samples used to investigate the finance-growth nexus. Consequently, previous studies led to mixed results and different conclusions. Most studies that used panel data applied models such as fixed/random effect or least square dummy variable (LSDV), assuming homogeneity of impact across countries. Studies also used the generalized method of moments (GMM) estimation method for dynamic panel data, considering it superior to other methods.

However, Nickell (1981) argues that the FE and RE results are biased and inconsistent. At the same time, Kiviet (1995), Bruno (2005b, 2005a), Bun, and Carree (2006) indicate that the results produced using the LSDV and GMM estimators are also erratic and suffer from finite-sample biases.

Hence, we turn to the bias-corrected LSDV estimator (LSDVC) developed by Kiviet (1995) and use the 'xtlsdvc' command in Stata developed by Bruno (Bruno, 2005b). Judson and Owen (1999) and Flannery & Hankins (2013) discuss the differences between these techniques. In short, when it comes to balanced panels, as is the case with our sample and all T lengths, the LSDVC estimation technique is superior to all other estimation techniques mentioned above. Using the LSDVC estimation technique, we get the bootstrapped standard errors that are computing via Monte Carlo simulations with 50 replications.

Thus, to assess the impact of financial development and institutional quality on economic growth, we use the following dynamic panel data model (Agbloyor et al., 2016; Compton & Giedeman, 2011):

$$GDP_{it} = \alpha GDP_{it-1} + \beta FD_{it} + \delta ID_{it} + \theta X_{it} + \mu_i + \eta_t + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (Eq. 1)$$

where for country i (the cross-sectional dimension) at time t (the time dimension), GDP_{it} is the log of annual real per capita GDP growth rate, GDP_{it-1} is the lagged value of the log of annual real per capita GDP growth rate, FD_{it} is a measure of financial development, ID_{it} is a measure of institutional development, X_{it} is a vector of all control variables; μ_i is a country-specific effect, η_t is a time-specific effect, and ε_{it} is a random error term that captures all other variables.

³ Although the euro was officially launched on 1 January 1999, the physical notes and coins were introduced only on 1 January 2002.

As pointed out earlier, there is potential non-linearity in the finance-growth nexus. Hence, we will test this using square terms of financial development indicators as illustrated in the following model:

$$GDP_{it} = \alpha GDP_{it-1} + \beta FD_{it} + \gamma FD_{it}^2 + \delta ID_{it} + \theta X_{it} + \mu_i + \eta_t + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (Eq. 2)$$

where FD_{it}^2 represents the square term of our financial development measures. Finally, to test whether the impact of financial development depends on the level of institutional development, we introduce an interaction term to **Eq. (1)** as presented in **Eq. (3)** below. These interaction terms allow us to distinguish the direct and indirect impacts of financial and institutional development on growth. As suggested by Brambor, Clark, & Golder (2006), we include all relevant terms in the interaction model specification as follows:

$$GDP_{it} = \alpha GDP_{it-1} + \beta FD_{it} + \delta ID_{it} + \vartheta (FD_{it} \times ID_{it}) + \theta X_{it} + \mu_i + \eta_t + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (Eq. 3)$$

where, $FD_{it} \times ID_{it}$ represents the interaction variable. Other terms are as defined earlier.

4. EMPIRICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Results and Discussion

Table 3, **Table 4**, and **Table 5** present the estimated results for linear, non-linear, and interaction models based on *Eq (1)*, *Eq (2)*, and *Eq (3)* respectively. In all these tables, we are using financial institutions (FI), financial markets (FM), liquid liabilities (LL), and private credit (PC) as proxies for financial development and the Heritage Institutional Development Index (ID) as a proxy for institutional development. In each table, we have twelve models, four for each sample: all (overall) countries, EU countries, and transition economies (TE) sample.

Now, we move to the discussion of linear relation results presented in **Table 3**. This table tests our first hypothesis (H_1): that finance contributes to economic growth. In general, however, the results show that FI and PC significantly negatively impact economic growth in the overall and EU sample countries. At the same time, LL exhibits a similar impact only in the overall sample. These results align with Mihci (2006), and Swamy and Dharani (2019), but in contrast to the claims of Rousseau and Wachtel (2011), who point to the fact that the finance-growth relationship is fading.

In contrast, the impact of FM on economic growth is insignificant in all subsamples with different signs. Financial development, however, is negligible in the case of TE with a positive sign except when LL is used as a proxy for financial development, which shows a negative sign. We can attribute these results to the transitional nature of these countries that recently moved from control-based to market-based economies. During this process, they started financial liberalization without proper expertise, which made their markets open and vulnerable to international factors. All these contribute to the overall instabilities in those economies that could consequently make financial development ineffective. In brief, based on the results, we cannot confirm (H_1).

Surprisingly, however, institutional development (ID) sourced from the Heritage Foundation has an insignificant and predominantly negative impact on economic growth. This contrasts previous studies that showed a significant effect of ID on growth Singh et al. (2009), Nguyen et al. (2018), and Kutan et al. (2017). Thus, although financial and institutional development differs in the EU and TE samples, the results indicate that no institutions impact economic growth. Reasons for these somewhat strange results could be that (i) the effect of institutional development has been amalgamated with financial development proxies in the case of EU countries, and (ii) institutions in TE countries are way too immature to make any significant contribution to growth either directly or indirectly

via financial development. These countries underwent rapid privatization and market liberalization while lacking proper legal and regulatory infrastructure. It may be due to these facts that both financial and institutional developments are insignificant in these countries. Rousseau and Wachtel (2011) report similar conclusions.

Table 3: The institutions-finance-growth nexus: linear models using GDP & ID

VARIABLES	(1) ALL	(2) ALL	(3) ALL	(4) ALL	(5) EU	(6) EU	(7) EU	(8) EU	(9) TE	(10) TE	(11) TE	(12) TE
GDP _{t-1}	0.144*** (0.048)	0.154*** (0.049)	0.153*** (0.040)	0.126*** (0.048)	0.111** (0.045)	0.129*** (0.045)	0.127*** (0.045)	0.092** (0.045)	0.106 (0.127)	0.064 (0.125)	0.131 (0.091)	0.132 (0.091)
FI	-0.177* (0.093)				-0.334** (0.165)				0.126 (0.328)			
FM		0.034 (0.036)				-0.025 (0.046)				0.108 (0.083)		
LL			-0.130* (0.074)				-0.080 (0.113)				-0.021 (0.154)	
PC				-0.150*** (0.044)				-0.184*** (0.054)				0.005 (0.123)
ID	-0.076 (0.298)	-0.311 (0.239)	-0.178 (0.274)	-0.085 (0.228)	0.011 (0.357)	-0.358 (0.290)	-0.300 (0.316)	-0.164 (0.238)	0.001 (0.653)	0.370 (0.641)	-0.208 (0.567)	-0.225 (0.535)
TO	0.420*** (0.119)	0.446*** (0.117)	0.411*** (0.111)	0.392*** (0.111)	0.755*** (0.173)	0.752*** (0.173)	0.737*** (0.173)	0.725*** (0.201)	0.034 (0.287)	0.025 (0.304)	0.253 (0.314)	0.231 (0.334)
GCF	0.252*** (0.094)	0.239*** (0.092)	0.219*** (0.081)	0.209*** (0.073)	0.363*** (0.095)	0.335*** (0.093)	0.315*** (0.096)	0.313*** (0.091)	-0.174 (0.243)	-0.218 (0.234)	0.066 (0.174)	0.062 (0.174)
EXP	-0.201 (0.146)	-0.261* (0.140)	-0.208 (0.142)	-0.114 (0.142)	-0.139 (0.192)	-0.178 (0.188)	-0.156 (0.197)	-0.032 (0.193)	-0.425 (0.399)	-0.422 (0.342)	-0.325 (0.295)	-0.330 (0.297)
HC	-0.364 (0.350)	-0.274 (0.349)	-0.384* (0.232)	-0.340 (0.318)	-0.264 (0.298)	-0.170 (0.297)	-0.155 (0.296)	-0.106 (0.200)	-1.025 (0.986)	-1.337 (0.969)	-0.764 (0.650)	-0.760 (0.644)
INF	0.209*** (0.057)	0.215*** (0.057)	0.207*** (0.053)	0.205*** (0.051)	0.357*** (0.041)	0.363*** (0.040)	0.366*** (0.040)	0.351*** (0.048)	-0.273* (0.144)	-0.254* (0.141)	-0.221 (0.138)	-0.220 (0.138)
Year dummies	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Observations	635	635	635	635	466	466	466	466	169	169	169	169
# of countries	38	38	38	38	28	28	28	28	10	10	10	10

Note: Bias correction initialized by Arellano and Bond estimator. Bias approximation is accurate up to $O(1/NT)$. Bootstrapped standard errors using 50 iterations. Standard errors in parentheses. Significance level *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.10$. The dependent variable is GDP per capita. GDP_{t-1} is the lagged dependent variable. FI - financial institutions, FM - financial markets, LL - liquid liabilities to GDP, PC - private credit to GDP, ID - institutional development, TO - trade openness, GCF - gross capital formation, EXP - government consumption expenditure, HC - human capital, INF - inflation. All variables are in log form.

When it comes to control variables, the results indicate that the lagged dependent variable (GDP_{t-1}), trade openness (TO), gross capital formations (GCF), and inflation (INF) have a significantly positive impact on growth in all models but the TE sample. The overall effect of government expenditure (EXP) and human capital (HC) is insignificant, excluding models (2) and (3), where they are, respectively, found to have a significantly negative impact on growth. Again, all control variables are statistically insignificant for transition economies. Inflation is the only control variable that negatively and significantly impacts growth in models (10) and (11).

Testing for the possible non-linear relationships between finance and growth (H_2), we move to **Table 4**, which reports results based on Eq (2) above. Integrating square terms into our baseline model made most financial development proxies insignificant, although with the same signs. The negative impact of financial development on growth is confirmed for LL and PC in the EU sample, and the results align with the results from **Table 3**. However, our results do not support a non-linear relationship in our sample countries, as most financial development square terms are insignificant. A non-linear relationship is only detected in model (7), EU sample, where liquid liabilities are used as a proxy for financial development. Our results indicate a U-shaped relationship between finance

and growth, contrasting findings reported by Swamy and Dharani (2019), Law and Singh (2014), and Prochniak and Wasiaik (2017), who found an inverted U-shaped relationship. As for control variables, the results conform to previously reported results from [Table 3](#).

Table 4: The institutions-finance-growth nexus: non-linear models using GDP & ID

VARIABLES	(1) ALL	(2) ALL	(3) ALL	(4) ALL	(5) EU	(6) EU	(7) EU	(8) EU	(9) TE	(10) TE	(11) TE	(12) TE
GDP _{t-1}	0.144*** (0.048)	0.154*** (0.050)	0.152*** (0.041)	0.122** (0.048)	0.110** (0.045)	0.130*** (0.045)	0.111** (0.044)	0.092** (0.044)	0.110 (0.132)	0.070 (0.129)	0.137 (0.092)	0.141 (0.091)
FI	-0.324 (0.261)				-0.241 (0.286)				0.211 (1.515)			
FISQR	-0.074 (0.124)				0.073 (0.211)				0.037 (0.629)			
FM		-0.007 (0.132)				-0.029 (0.117)				0.183 (0.531)		
FMSQR		-0.006 (0.018)				-0.001 (0.026)				0.010 (0.070)		
LL			-0.513 (0.327)				-1.419** (0.631)				-0.156 (1.269)	
LLSQR			0.052 (0.041)				0.147** (0.070)				0.021 (0.196)	
PC				0.053 (0.197)				-0.750** (0.365)				0.435 (0.484)
PCSQR				-0.030 (0.028)				0.071 (0.045)				-0.073 (0.077)
ID	-0.081 (0.300)	-0.311 (0.239)	-0.122 (0.291)	-0.111 (0.226)	0.019 (0.361)	-0.357 (0.293)	-0.137 (0.327)	-0.054 (0.257)	0.023 (0.635)	0.379 (0.652)	-0.209 (0.565)	-0.290 (0.526)
TO	0.424*** (0.121)	0.449*** (0.118)	0.417*** (0.112)	0.388*** (0.110)	0.765*** (0.177)	0.750*** (0.175)	0.804*** (0.180)	0.756*** (0.201)	0.031 (0.311)	0.024 (0.309)	0.241 (0.314)	0.294 (0.337)
GCF	0.253*** (0.094)	0.243*** (0.091)	0.227*** (0.082)	0.196*** (0.075)	0.369*** (0.099)	0.334*** (0.094)	0.336*** (0.096)	0.339*** (0.090)	-0.178 (0.252)	-0.222 (0.242)	0.059 (0.172)	0.079 (0.171)
EXP	-0.204 (0.147)	-0.257* (0.139)	-0.219 (0.142)	-0.112 (0.143)	-0.145 (0.194)	-0.179 (0.189)	-0.144 (0.196)	-0.134 (0.199)	-0.420 (0.413)	-0.431 (0.367)	-0.324 (0.300)	-0.370 (0.300)
HC	-0.372 (0.354)	-0.279 (0.350)	-0.403* (0.230)	-0.302 (0.326)	-0.287 (0.307)	-0.171 (0.299)	-0.151 (0.294)	-0.179 (0.201)	-1.002 (1.006)	-1.308 (0.964)	-0.757 (0.662)	-0.835 (0.650)
INF	0.209*** (0.057)	0.214*** (0.057)	0.206*** (0.053)	0.200*** (0.051)	0.354*** (0.040)	0.363*** (0.040)	0.361*** (0.040)	0.350*** (0.047)	-0.272** (0.138)	-0.252* (0.143)	-0.219 (0.140)	-0.230* (0.137)
Year dummies	YES	YES	YES	YES								
Observations	635	635	635	635	466	466	466	466	169	169	169	169
# of countries	38	38	38	38	28	28	28	28	10	10	10	10

Note: Bias correction initialized by Arellano and Bond estimator. Bias approximation is accurate up to $O(1/NT)$. Bootstrapped standard errors using 50 iterations. Standard errors in parentheses. Significance level *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.10. The dependent variable is GDP per capita. GDP_{t-1} is the lagged dependent variable, FI - financial institutions, FISQR - square term of FI, FM - financial markets, FMSQR - square term of FM, LL - liquid liabilities to GDP, LLSQR - square term of LL, PC - private credit to GDP, PCSQR - square term of PC, ID - institutional development, TO - trade openness, GCF - gross capital formation, EXP - government consumption expenditure, HC - human capital, INF - inflation. All variables are in log form.

[Table 5](#) below provides results based on [Eq \(3\)](#) and investigates whether finance's impact on growth depends on institutions (H_3). Having interaction terms in our models makes all our financial development proxies insignificant. While insignificant, the majority of financial development proxies change their signs. Institutional development is only significant, with a direct negative impact on growth in the model (2). However, our primary focus variables, interaction terms, are all insignificant with different signs. Hence, our results reject H_3 . This aligns with studies by Minea & Villieu (2010), Djeri et al. (2020), and Slesman et al. (2019), who claim that institutional quality should reach a certain threshold for finance to affect growth positively. This may sound realistic for TE countries as their institutions could be more developed. However, this explanation may only apply to some EU sample countries with well-developed institutions. As pointed out briefly above, a possible

explanation could be that institutional development effects are already fused into other factors affecting economic growth, including but not limited to finance. All other control variables align with previous results reported in [Table 3](#) and [Table 4](#).

Table 5: The institutions-finance-growth nexus: interaction models using GDP & ID

VARIABLES	(1) ALL	(2) ALL	(3) ALL	(4) ALL	(5) EU	(6) EU	(7) EU	(8) EU	(9) TE	(10) TE	(11) TE	(12) TE
GDPT-1	0.145*** (0.048)	0.153*** (0.049)	0.154*** (0.040)	0.127*** (0.047)	0.110** (0.045)	0.130*** (0.045)	0.128*** (0.046)	0.092** (0.044)	0.095 (0.122)	0.069 (0.129)	0.119 (0.093)	0.128 (0.095)
FI	0.964 (1.947)				3.409 (2.563)				-6.158 (6.557)			
FIxID	-0.277 (0.471)				-0.908 (0.613)				1.500 (1.585)			
FM		0.617 (0.574)				0.641 (0.948)				-0.061 (1.536)		
FMxID		-0.145 (0.142)				-0.160 (0.229)				0.043 (0.387)		
LL			-0.241 (0.915)				-0.190 (1.722)				-2.611 (2.639)	
LLxID			0.027 (0.220)				0.025 (0.406)				0.648 (0.658)	
PC				0.107 (0.912)				1.180 (1.130)				-2.236 (1.992)
PCxID				-0.062 (0.220)				-0.326 (0.266)				0.540 (0.482)
ID	-0.332 (0.498)	-0.664* (0.400)	-0.278 (0.805)	0.134 (0.853)	-0.538 (0.489)	-0.615 (0.417)	-0.396 (1.659)	1.073 (1.006)	2.018 (2.125)	0.519 (1.534)	-2.279 (2.174)	-1.971 (1.621)
TO	0.428*** (0.123)	0.448*** (0.117)	0.409*** (0.111)	0.391*** (0.110)	0.732*** (0.175)	0.741*** (0.176)	0.738*** (0.179)	0.706*** (0.201)	0.003 (0.289)	0.020 (0.310)	0.173 (0.314)	0.250 (0.333)
GCF	0.252*** (0.094)	0.245*** (0.092)	0.218*** (0.082)	0.205*** (0.074)	0.342*** (0.099)	0.337*** (0.093)	0.316*** (0.097)	0.301*** (0.089)	-0.280 (0.291)	-0.219 (0.238)	0.029 (0.175)	0.033 (0.177)
EXP	-0.173 (0.148)	-0.233 (0.144)	-0.215 (0.154)	-0.098 (0.173)	-0.114 (0.197)	-0.166 (0.192)	-0.156 (0.201)	0.034 (0.188)	-0.614 (0.507)	-0.426 (0.342)	-0.449 (0.306)	-0.499 (0.326)
HC	-0.354 (0.358)	-0.263 (0.352)	-0.388* (0.230)	-0.331 (0.319)	-0.174 (0.312)	-0.112 (0.305)	-0.157 (0.307)	-0.018 (0.212)	-1.124 (0.979)	-1.317 (1.015)	-0.689 (0.669)	-0.665 (0.662)
INF	0.212*** (0.057)	0.219*** (0.057)	0.206*** (0.054)	0.206*** (0.050)	0.366*** (0.040)	0.365*** (0.040)	0.365*** (0.040)	0.358*** (0.046)	-0.310** (0.156)	-0.255* (0.142)	-0.227 (0.139)	-0.239* (0.140)
Year dummies	YES	YES	YES	YES								
Observations	635	635	635	635	466	466	466	466	169	169	169	169
# of countries	38	38	38	38	28	28	28	28	10	10	10	10

Note: Bias correction initialized by Arellano and Bond estimator. Bias approximation is accurate up to $O(1/NT)$. Bootstrapped standard errors using 50 iterations. Standard errors in parentheses. Significance level *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.10$. The dependent variable is GDP per capita. GDP_{t-1} is the lagged dependent variable, FI - financial institutions, FIxID - interaction term between FI and ID, FM - financial markets, FMxID - interaction term between FM and ID, LL - liquid liabilities to GDP, LLxID - interaction term between LL and ID, PC - private credit to GDP, PCxID - interaction term between PC and ID, ID - institutional development, TO - trade openness, GCF - gross capital formation, EXP - government consumption expenditure, HC - human capital, INF - inflation. All variables are in log form.

4.2. Robustness Tests

As for robustness tests, we run the same estimations using GDP growth as our dependent variable, and the institutional development index constructed PCA method based on six WGI indicators. All tables for robustness tests are reported in Appendix 1. [Table A1.1](#) provides estimation results for our baseline model. Our results remain unchanged, and the results from [Table 3](#) are confirmed. As for the non-linear relationship, the robustness results in [Table A1.2](#) support our previous finding in [Table 4](#). However, besides model (7), these results show more evidence of non-linearity in model (3) for the

overall sample and model (8) for the EU sample. All these cases confirm the U-shaped relationship between finance and growth. Control variables are, nevertheless, in line with previous results.

Similarly, robustness tests for interaction models are presented in [Table A1.3](#). Although our main results in [Table 5](#) showed the insignificance of finance and institutions and their interaction terms, our robustness results are somehow different. While most results conform with the main results, three models confirm the negative and one positive significance of financial development on growth. At the same time, the interaction term in model (6), FMxIQ, is also found to have a significantly negative impact on economic growth. In other words, under this model, the effect of financial markets depends on institutional development. However, as most interaction terms are insignificant, we can conclude that institutions do not affect growth directly or via finance. At the same time, results for transition economies in [Table A1.1](#), [Table A1.2](#), and [Table A1.3](#) are consistent with the leading results reported earlier in [Table 3](#), [Table 4](#), and [Table 5](#).

The present findings seem consistent with other research that found the finance-growth nexus dependable on the financial development proxies used (Fernandez & Galetovic, 1994; De Gregorio & Guidotti, 1995; Luintel & Khan, 1999; Ram, 1999; Naceur & Ghazouani, 2007; Favara, 2003; Hsueh et al., 2013; Carré & Lœillet, 2018; Nyasha & Odhiambo, 2018). At the same time, these findings further support the idea that this relationship depends on financial and institutional development levels within sample countries. Hence, we found support for our H_4 and H_5 hypotheses.

Finally, it is essential to note that our results are robust to different combinations of two dependent and two institutional development proxies. These results are not reported but are available upon a reasonable request.

5. CONCLUSION

The study revisits the finance-growth relationship by focusing on EU and transition economies and considering institutional development. Our results reveal that the impact of financial development on economic growth is generally negative when overall and EU samples are considered. The effect is, however, insignificant when a transitional economies sample is used. Furthermore, even though financial and institutional development is at different levels in EU and TE sample countries, the results indicate no impact of institutions on economic growth at all. The effects of institutions are integrated within financial development proxies in the case of the EU, and these institutions are immature in transition economies to impact growth.

All in all, our primary and robustness results indicate that the impact of finance on growth is either significantly negative or insignificant altogether, and this relationship is primarily linear. In addition, institutions have no direct or indirect (via finance) impact on growth in all our samples. Hence, we find no support for our hypotheses H_1 , H_2 , and H_3 . However, the evidence supports H_4 and H_5 , showing that the finance-growth nexus depends on the proxies used for financial development and the level of financial and institutional development within sample countries.

Declarations

The author has no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose. The data are available upon a reasonable request from the author.

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APPENDIX 1

A1. ROBUSTNESS TESTS

Table A1.1: *The institutions-finance-growth nexus: robustness test for linear models using GDPG & ID*

VARIABLES	(1) ALL	(2) ALL	(3) ALL	(4) ALL	(5) EU	(6) EU	(7) EU	(8) EU	(9) TE	(10) TE	(11) TE	(12) TE
GDPG _{t-1}	0.095** (0.048)	0.103** (0.048)	0.108*** (0.039)	0.085* (0.048)	0.110** (0.046)	0.131*** (0.045)	0.126*** (0.046)	0.088** (0.044)	0.076 (0.127)	0.049 (0.128)	0.088 (0.095)	0.086 (0.093)
FI	-0.256** (0.107)				-0.340** (0.135)				0.019 (0.426)			
FM		0.050 (0.045)				-0.032 (0.046)				0.111 (0.095)		
LL			-0.156* (0.087)				-0.126 (0.108)				-0.054 (0.195)	
PC				-0.188*** (0.054)				-0.199*** (0.055)				0.036 (0.150)
IQ	0.245 (0.197)	0.062 (0.172)	0.160 (0.184)	0.278 (0.179)	0.123 (0.183)	0.090 (0.183)	0.112 (0.189)	0.190 (0.172)	0.416 (0.375)	0.434 (0.325)	0.356 (0.417)	0.325 (0.385)
TO	0.476*** (0.146)	0.502*** (0.145)	0.453*** (0.139)	0.439*** (0.137)	0.735*** (0.173)	0.726*** (0.174)	0.701*** (0.175)	0.683*** (0.204)	0.080 (0.330)	0.097 (0.355)	0.265 (0.383)	0.179 (0.401)
GCF	0.351*** (0.116)	0.328*** (0.115)	0.276*** (0.099)	0.246*** (0.093)	0.351*** (0.098)	0.302*** (0.095)	0.277*** (0.098)	0.278*** (0.095)	-0.197 (0.302)	-0.242 (0.294)	0.039 (0.217)	0.033 (0.219)
EXP	-0.179 (0.174)	-0.227 (0.173)	-0.180 (0.174)	-0.098 (0.186)	-0.169 (0.198)	-0.228 (0.196)	-0.192 (0.204)	-0.080 (0.193)	-0.453 (0.493)	-0.533 (0.457)	-0.379 (0.392)	-0.393 (0.377)
HC	-0.381 (0.438)	-0.255 (0.437)	-0.358 (0.294)	-0.276 (0.402)	-0.260 (0.301)	-0.108 (0.303)	-0.101 (0.303)	-0.068 (0.202)	-1.182 (1.149)	-1.351 (1.151)	-0.634 (0.788)	-0.626 (0.783)
INF	0.357*** (0.069)	0.374*** (0.070)	0.361*** (0.066)	0.354*** (0.064)	0.359*** (0.041)	0.370*** (0.040)	0.374*** (0.041)	0.356*** (0.048)	-0.339** (0.172)	-0.334** (0.163)	-0.249 (0.177)	-0.242 (0.177)
Year dummies	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Observations	635	635	635	635	466	466	466	466	169	169	169	169
# of countries	38	38	38	38	28	28	28	28	10	10	10	10

Note: Bias correction initialized by Arellano and Bond estimator. Bias approximation is accurate up to $O(1/NT)$. Bootstrapped standard errors using 50 iterations. Standard errors in parentheses. Significance level *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.10$. The dependent variable is GDP growth. GDPG_{t-1} is the lagged dependent variable, FI - financial institutions, FM - financial markets, LL - liquid liabilities to GDP, PC - private credit to GDP, IQ - institutional quality, TO - trade openness, GCF - gross capital formation, EXP - government consumption expenditure, HC - human capital, INF - inflation. All variables are in log form.

Table A1.2: The institutions-finance-growth nexus: robustness test for non-linear models using GDPG & ID

VARIABLES	(1) ALL	(2) ALL	(3) ALL	(4) ALL	(5) EU	(6) EU	(7) EU	(8) EU	(9) TE	(10) TE	(11) TE	(12) TE
GDPG _{t-1}	0.095** (0.047)	0.103** (0.049)	0.106*** (0.039)	0.083* (0.048)	0.110** (0.045)	0.132*** (0.045)	0.104** (0.044)	0.089** (0.044)	0.081 (0.131)	0.047 (0.132)	0.093 (0.095)	0.093 (0.094)
FI	-0.300 (0.310)				-0.248 (0.280)				0.351 (1.827)			
FISQR	-0.023 (0.157)				0.071 (0.210)				0.141 (0.747)			
FM		0.036 (0.164)				-0.030 (0.118)				-0.041 (0.681)		
FMSQR		-0.002 (0.022)				0.000 (0.027)				-0.020 (0.092)		
LL			-0.877** (0.433)				-1.793*** (0.647)				-0.418 (1.538)	
LLSQR			0.097* (0.054)				0.184** (0.072)				0.057 (0.237)	
PC				-0.049 (0.249)				-0.796** (0.332)				0.595 (0.587)
PCSQR				-0.021 (0.036)				0.076* (0.042)				-0.095 (0.093)
IQ	0.243 (0.201)	0.062 (0.171)	0.279 (0.209)	0.263 (0.179)	0.120 (0.184)	0.089 (0.183)	0.274 (0.199)	0.200 (0.169)	0.430 (0.376)	0.471 (0.351)	0.368 (0.415)	0.298 (0.381)
TO	0.479*** (0.148)	0.503*** (0.147)	0.467*** (0.140)	0.436*** (0.138)	0.746*** (0.177)	0.724*** (0.175)	0.767*** (0.180)	0.719*** (0.205)	0.078 (0.339)	0.089 (0.364)	0.239 (0.383)	0.252 (0.405)
GCF	0.350*** (0.116)	0.329*** (0.114)	0.288*** (0.100)	0.237** (0.096)	0.357*** (0.102)	0.301*** (0.096)	0.302*** (0.098)	0.312*** (0.096)	-0.214 (0.311)	-0.242 (0.296)	0.023 (0.216)	0.053 (0.215)
EXP	-0.181 (0.175)	-0.225 (0.173)	-0.227 (0.175)	-0.093 (0.188)	-0.173 (0.200)	-0.228 (0.198)	-0.204 (0.201)	-0.187 (0.196)	-0.452 (0.496)	-0.525 (0.473)	-0.376 (0.394)	-0.428 (0.385)
HC	-0.384 (0.440)	-0.258 (0.438)	-0.376 (0.291)	-0.249 (0.414)	-0.282 (0.310)	-0.110 (0.306)	-0.115 (0.298)	-0.163 (0.204)	-1.084 (1.225)	-1.392 (1.146)	-0.602 (0.801)	-0.723 (0.783)
INF	0.357*** (0.069)	0.374*** (0.070)	0.357*** (0.066)	0.350*** (0.065)	0.356*** (0.040)	0.370*** (0.040)	0.365*** (0.041)	0.354*** (0.048)	-0.340** (0.173)	-0.338** (0.167)	-0.245 (0.179)	-0.248 (0.177)
Year dummies	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES						
Observations	635	635	635	635	466	466	466	466	169	169	169	169
# of countries	38	38	38	38	28	28	28	28	10	10	10	10

Note: Bias correction initialized by Arellano and Bond estimator. Bias approximation is accurate up to $O(1/NT)$. Bootstrapped standard errors using 50 iterations. Standard errors in parentheses. Significance level *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.10$. The dependent variable is GDP growth. GDP_{t-1} is the lagged dependent variable, FI - financial institutions, FISQR - square term of FI, FM - financial markets, FMSQR - square term of FM, LL - liquid liabilities to GDP, LLSQR - square term of LL, PC - private credit to GDP, PCSQR - square term of PC, IQ - institutional quality, TO - trade openness, GCF - gross capital formation, EXP - government consumption expenditure, HC - human capital, INF - inflation. All variables are in log form.

Table A1.3: The institutions-finance-growth nexus: robustness test for interaction models using GDPG & ID

VARIABLES	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)
	ALL	ALL	ALL	ALL	EU	EU	EU	EU	TE	TE	TE	TE
GDPG _{t-1}	0.095** (0.047)	0.103** (0.048)	0.109*** (0.039)	0.087* (0.048)	0.111** (0.046)	0.127*** (0.044)	0.125*** (0.046)	0.088** (0.044)	0.080 (0.133)	0.055 (0.130)	0.092 (0.094)	0.063 (0.096)
FI	-0.172 (0.159)				-0.155 (0.269)				-0.074 (0.655)			
FlxIQ	-0.209 (0.265)				-0.271 (0.310)				0.178 (1.105)			
FM		0.077 (0.055)				0.154 (0.101)				0.084 (0.129)		
FMxIQ		-0.064 (0.088)				-0.258** (0.111)				0.105 (0.323)		
LL			-0.226* (0.116)				-0.322* (0.189)				-0.133 (0.224)	
LLxIQ			0.196 (0.164)				0.253 (0.230)				0.380 (0.632)	
PC				-0.214*** (0.069)				-0.277** (0.128)				-0.131 (0.188)
PCxIQ				0.076 (0.117)				0.099 (0.145)				0.637* (0.353)
IQ	0.074 (0.283)	-0.108 (0.299)	-0.565 (0.605)	-0.007 (0.491)	-0.014 (0.224)	-0.226 (0.228)	-0.994 (1.019)	-0.237 (0.666)	0.594 (1.156)	0.824 (1.245)	-1.000 (2.361)	-2.063 (1.353)
TO	0.493*** (0.146)	0.507*** (0.145)	0.457*** (0.139)	0.437*** (0.137)	0.731*** (0.175)	0.672*** (0.176)	0.724*** (0.175)	0.699*** (0.205)	0.083 (0.333)	0.082 (0.358)	0.241 (0.382)	0.172 (0.402)
GCF	0.357*** (0.113)	0.338*** (0.113)	0.270*** (0.099)	0.248*** (0.094)	0.340*** (0.102)	0.316*** (0.096)	0.267*** (0.098)	0.283*** (0.093)	-0.213 (0.326)	-0.253 (0.304)	-0.003 (0.215)	-0.083 (0.220)
EXP	-0.179 (0.174)	-0.230 (0.175)	-0.223 (0.179)	-0.111 (0.190)	-0.161 (0.202)	-0.265 (0.199)	-0.268 (0.224)	-0.125 (0.208)	-0.436 (0.507)	-0.529 (0.462)	-0.355 (0.401)	-0.300 (0.383)
HC	-0.359 (0.445)	-0.259 (0.439)	-0.434 (0.287)	-0.306 (0.413)	-0.219 (0.317)	-0.101 (0.304)	-0.204 (0.318)	-0.095 (0.200)	-1.228 (1.137)	-1.302 (1.168)	-0.595 (0.809)	-0.521 (0.791)
INF	0.357*** (0.069)	0.373*** (0.070)	0.358*** (0.066)	0.357*** (0.065)	0.363*** (0.041)	0.371*** (0.040)	0.367*** (0.041)	0.351*** (0.047)	-0.343* (0.177)	-0.338** (0.165)	-0.239 (0.176)	-0.210 (0.172)
Year dummies	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Observations	635	635	635	635	466	466	466	466	169	169	169	169
# of countries	38	38	38	38	28	28	28	28	10	10	10	10

Note: Bias correction initialized by Arellano and Bond estimator. Bias approximation is accurate up to $O(1/NT)$. Bootstrapped standard errors using 50 iterations. Standard errors in parentheses. Significance level *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.10$. The dependent variable is GDP growth. GDP_{t-1} is the lagged dependent variable, FI - financial institutions, FlxIQ - interaction term between FI and IQ, FM - financial markets, FMxIQ - interaction term between FM and IQ, LL - liquid liabilities to GDP, LLxIQ - interaction term between LL and IQ, PC - private credit to GDP, PCxIQ - interaction term between PC and IQ, IQ - institutional quality, TO - trade openness, GCF - gross capital formation, EXP - government consumption expenditure, HC - human capital, INF - inflation. All variables are in log form.

The Role of Demographics in Green Purchase Intentions: Evidence from Jordan, the United Arab Emirates, and the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the role that demographic factors (country of origin, age, gender, and education) play in green purchase intentions (GPIs) among consumers in Jordan, the United Arab Emirates, and the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA). It is based on primary, quantitative, cross-sectional data collected using the questionnaire. The final sample included 680 consumers from the three countries. Hypotheses are tested using the independent samples t-test and one-way ANOVA. Results of the study show that age, gender, and education are not significant differentiators in GPI, while partial support was found regarding the role of country of origin. The study points out the relevance of GPIs and indicates the theoretical and practical implications. It enriches the scarce literature on green consumer behavior in the Middle East region and presents future research suggestions for its further development.

ARTICLE HISTORY

Received: May 27, 2024

Accepted: June 2, 2024

Published: June 30, 2024

KEYWORDS

green purchase intention; Jordan; United Arab Emirates; Kingdom of Saudi Arabia; Middle East

JEL CODES

D12; E21; N35;

HOW TO CITE

Knezović, E., Hamarsheh, A. G. Y., & Smajić, H. (2024). The Role of Demographics in Green Purchase Intentions: Evidence from Jordan, the United Arab Emirates, and the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. *Journal of Economics, Law and Society*, 1(1), 23-38. <https://doi.org/10.70009/jels.2024.1.1.2>

1. INTRODUCTION

In 2016, the World Health Organization (WHO) published an article showing that 12.6 million deaths annually and almost 25% of all diseases worldwide are due to avoidable environmental causes. Diseases and health issues linked to the environment include asthma, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, cardiovascular diseases, etc. To curb the pollution causing these maladies, the Center for Disease Control and Prevention (2018) recommends sustainable food choices, using alternative means of transportation, and purchasing eco-friendly or green products. Sustainability concerns contributed to the emergence of green marketing, international firms' focus on green production, and consumers' focus on green purchasing (Zaremohzzabieh et al., 2021).

In the Middle East region, specifically Jordan, the United Arab Emirates (UAE), and the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA), the importance of consuming environmentally friendly products is ever-increasing for several reasons. The most pressing one is the immediate and direct effect of the consumption of green products on human health. Additionally, the region is especially vulnerable to air pollution. Deemed "the silent killer," the air in these countries is among the most toxic globally (Cooke, 2017).

All these problems in the region and the rest of the world have led to a growth in public awareness of the environment and its importance, which in turn has resulted in increased calls for changing consumption and purchasing habits next to enacting laws that lead to consumers' awareness about

the importance of environmental sustainability in their regions and communities.

Laroche et al. (2001) and Kilbourne et al. (2009) argued that consumers' awareness of environmental problems related to their consumption will make it more likely that consumers will seek to purchase environmentally green products for the benefit of future generations. During the last decades, the focus on sustainability among consumers has been on the rise, accompanied by increased environmental concerns among companies' CEOs around the globe (Uddin & Khan, 2016).

Whereas the substantial research interest in and awareness of the environment had begun in the second half of the 20th century (e.g., Kinnear et al., 1974; Leonard-Barton, 1981; Alwitt & Pitts, 1996), there remains a gap in the understanding of consumer behavior regarding purchasing green products. De Moura et al. (2012) and Verbeke et al. (2007) indicated that consumers retain the right to choose products and how to consume them while a growing interest in the concept of preserving the environment has also emerged as a parallel major concern. Nevertheless, as Kilbourne et al. (2009) explained, consumers do not appear to show any consistent preference for green products in the long term.

To further increase the knowledge on green consumer behavior, it is essential to investigate its determinants. According to Ajzen (1991), intention is the best predictor of an actual behavior. Although not every intention will result in a behavior, every behavior is preceded by an intention (Ajzen, 1991; Krueger et al., 2000). Therefore, understanding consumers' green purchase intention (GPI) would significantly contribute to increasing information on green consumer behavior as GPI is its fundamental element (Al-Adamat et al., 2020).

Currently, research on GPI and green consumer behavior in Jordan, UAE, and KSA is scarce. More research is needed to investigate the factors affecting them, while the existing studies have several limitations. For instance, Mohammed et al. (2020) have investigated the factors influencing green behavior among young consumers in the KSA. However, the study omitted remaining age groups and other demographic variables (e.g., education), which could affect green consumer behavior. Additionally, focusing only on outcomes (i.e., green consumer behavior) excludes a significant portion of consumers who might have high GPI but have not practiced the behavior for various reasons. Important environmental awareness and sustainability changes cannot be achieved if only those who already directly contribute to it are included. Therefore, studying GPI instead of green consumer behavior becomes even more important from this perspective.

Evidence suggests that demographic factors are highly relevant regarding purchase intentions (Bhat et al., 2021). Hence, this study aims to investigate the role of demographic factors in GPI among consumers from KSA, Jordan, and UAE using quantitative data. The study will answer the following research question:

RQ1: What is the role of demographic factors (country of residence, age, gender, and education) in green purchase intentions among consumers from KSA, Jordan, and UAE?

This study's results provide several contributions. From a theoretical perspective, the study enriches the scarce literature on GPI and the role played by demographic factors in the Middle East Region. From a practical perspective, in addition to raising awareness of environmental issues and green consumption, such knowledge helps companies to precisely target the most relevant customers for green products and carefully tailor their marketing strategies. They will understand which demographic groups already have high GPI that should now be converted to actual behavior and in which groups they need to stimulate such intentions. All of this will increase awareness and sales of green products, which will benefit society's overall health and wellbeing.

After the introduction, this paper presents the literature review and hypotheses, methods, results, and discussion and conclusions.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES

2.1. Green purchase intention

Chen and Chai (2010) defined green products as products with a limited environmental impact and incorporating strategies with recycled materials, reduced packaging, and less harmful substances. Kumar and Ghodeswar (2015) state that eco-friendly products are developed using healthy ingredients and environmentally friendly measures. Since the ecological development goals call for reducing energy use and lowering heat and pollutant emissions, applying these measures can help to maximize the sustainability of limited resources.

According to Vazifehdoust et al. (2013), green purchasing considers environmental criteria along with others, such as quality and price, during a purchase decision. *Figure 1* shows the process of purchase decisions (Kotler, 2012).

Figure 1: Process of making a purchase decision

Source: Kotler (2012)

Recognition means the consumer will realize the need for green products and the reasons behind them, whether it is a better lifestyle or to prevent a specific health issue. In the second stage, the consumer will search for all alternative products and collect more information about them. This leads them to the third step, which is evaluating the products. The consumer will rank every alternative product and compare them according to price, expectations, quality, and with traditional products. The consumer's green purchasing intent will also be affected by internal factors like desires and external factors like prices. In the next stage, the consumer will decide and buy the product. In the final stage, for evaluating the purchasing decision, consumers will ask themselves whether the green product met their expectations, whether the price and quality were acceptable, and whether the product had a noticeable effect on health and daily routine. If consumers are satisfied based on their experience, they will repeatedly purchase the green product in the future (Kotler, 2012).

However, to better understand the actual behavior of consumers regarding green products, it is essential to examine its predictors. As mentioned earlier, the most relevant predictors of actual behavior are precisely intentions (Ajzen, 1991). Additionally, Mohammed et al. (2020) asserted that GPIs are major factors influencing actual green consumer behavior.

Bagozzi et al. (1981) frame purchase intentions (PIs) as personal action tendencies relating to a brand or a specific product. Studying PIs thus helps companies define the factors that lead consumers to purchase a specific product type. Understanding PIs can help marketing managers predict the sales of new products and the possibility of repeating purchases of an existing product (Ali et al., 2011).

Based on the PIs' definition, GPIs can be defined as personal action tendencies toward green/eco-friendly products. Nowadays, a huge number of alternative options and attributes are available for each product, regardless of whether it is a green or a traditional one. On top of that, brands are competing against one another in all target markets (Hinrichs, 2003). All these new conditions

created the actual need to study consumers' GPI, which in turn will help companies and concerned parties understand consumer behavior and how to customize the product to meet the client's expectations, leading to increased profitability in the long run.

Subsequently, institutions are now beginning to realize the crucial importance of their services and products being geared toward customers in all markets. Thus, it is necessary to study business needs and ways to fulfill market requirements (Kotler, 1997). In this context, Weatherell et al. (2003) investigated the motivations of new (concerned) consumers to show a significant interest in (alternative) foods produced under more eco-friendly conditions, including organic agriculture, local supply systems, and general environmentally friendly production. The authors argue that consumers' focus has shifted from the product's prices, packaging, and appearance to its quality and environmental impact that can be traced to specific places. Interest in green alternative products is definitely growing.

2.2. Demographic variables and green purchase intentions

Different studies confirmed that the relationship between demographic factors and green consumer behavior (e.g., Fisher et al., 2012) or the interplay between demographics and GPIs (e.g., Wang et al., 2020; Bhat et al., 2021; In & Ahmad, 2018; Rahim et al., 2017; Chekima et al., 2016; Nath et al., 2015). However, the results reached by these studies are inconclusive which indicates that the role played by demographic factors in GPIs might be context sensitive. Although interest in sustainability research has been growing in the MENA region recently (Ahmad et al., 2022), the area still needs to be studied (Jamali et al., 2020). Therefore, analyzing the interaction between demographic factors and GPIs in Jordan, UAE, and KSA is valuable from multiple perspectives.

2.2.1. Country of residence

As stated before, GPIs are potentially context-specific and, therefore, can be different for people from different countries. Generally, sustainability concerns in the MENA region are interesting because some of its countries rely heavily on oil as the source of their wealth, which opposes environmental protection efforts (Jamali et al., 2020).

For instance, existing studies indicate that Jordanian consumers are environmentally conscious but still prefer traditional products (Alsmadi, 2007; Al-Adamat et al., 2020). UAE consumers share the same concerns and interests as Jordanian ones (Alameeri et al., 2018). Khaleeli et al. (2021) investigated green purchase intentions (GPI) with UEA consumers. The results show how Emirati consumers' awareness positively affected their intention to buy environmentally friendly products, regardless of their price, compared to traditional products. Considering the KSA, the country's economy depends on the oil industry, as with its neighbors. The magnitude of the oil industry also means that KSA faces serious environmental challenges, such as land degradation, desertification, and air pollution related to energy production (Groissböck et al., 2016). Additional problems are related to water supply and quality and solid waste management, caused by high individual consumption levels. Hence, the awareness and willingness of consumers to purchase green products are at least questionable.

Naturally, the government, structure of the economy, culture, etc., can significantly impact individual consumption preferences. Although Jordan, UAE, and the KSA share certain similarities in terms of the mentioned factors, the region is also characterized by diversity among people. Nevertheless, all three countries still need to be more researched regarding GPI and green consumer behavior. Hence, to contribute to a better understanding of GPIs in the region, this study is going to investigate the next hypothesis:

H1. There is a difference in green purchase intentions between consumers from Jordan, UAE, and KSA.

2.2.2. Age of respondents

Numerous studies explained that age is a frequently used segmentation variable for the market (Quester et al. 2007; Kotler & Keller, 2006; Peter & Olson, 2008). Kurtz and Boone (2006) explain that age is an important factor when purchasing and choosing a particular product. As Casalegno et al. (2022) stated, age is a relevant factor in the choice of green products.

The results of various studies investigating green consumer behavior in different age groups are mixed. Fisher et al. (2012) mentioned that younger people were more likely to exhibit environmentally friendly behaviors and also indicated that older people were more likely to do so. However, for instance, Finisterra do Paço et al. (2009) did not find any significant difference. Similarly, Han et al. (2011) indicated no significant differences in eco-friendly intentions across age.

Further, research by Kim et al. (2012) showed that sustainable hotels must target younger travelers or guests, especially 25-35-year-old guests because they are more willing to be accommodated at a sustainable or eco-friendly hotel than older age groups. However, Witek and Kuźniar (2020) stated in their work that young consumers are skeptical about green products.

The relevance of age is further confirmed as Al-Adamat et al. (2020) chose the age limit of 22 for their study of GPI since consumers in this age range are renowned for their green product purchase behaviors and feel empowered to choose the right items from the many available options.

Aapola (2002) confirms that age is key in empirical social research because it is used to categorize participants and explain their differences. Korpunen and Nápravníková (2008) show that people's experience could improve by increasing their age. Regarding GPI and socio-demographic factors, Straughan and Roberts (1999) stated that socio-demographic factors such as age, income, gender, and location were essential parameters to explain consumers' green preferences. Thus, the second hypothesis of this study is proposed:

H2. There is a difference in green purchase intentions due to age as a demographic factor.

2.2.3. Gender of respondents

Over time, multiple studies have investigated the relationship between gender and green consumer behavior. Findings by Gundala et al. (2022) indicated that gender plays a significant role in PI for organic foods. According to Fisher et al. (2012), females were found to have double the desire to buy environmentally friendly products than their male counterparts. This aligns with Witek and Kuźniar (2020), who stated that females have more positive attitudes towards purchasing green products. Such findings have become even more relevant since, in Western countries, many studies have pointed out that women make the decision to purchase green products more frequently than men (Banerjee & McKeage, 1994; Mostafa, 2007). Lee's (2009) research indicated that female adolescent consumers show higher eco-friendly interest and peer influence than male adolescents. From another perspective, Mo and Wong (2012) assert that consumers' gender influences their purchase intention by considering their income level. However, Li (2014) found that men are more likely to search for information on green products and to purchase such products, especially healthy food products. However, Masouleh et al. (2013) stated that gender-related studies' findings on eco-friendly products are still questionable and profiling green consumers using gender as the demographic variable is still indecisive. Therefore, to clarify the role of gender in GPIs, the third hypothesis is proposed:

H3. There is a difference in green purchase intentions due to gender as a demographic factor.

2.2.4. Education of respondents

The most consistent results were found for the role of education in green consumer behavior and its predictors. Shahnaei's (2012) research indicated that a higher education level positively impacts green purchasing among Malaysian consumers in the Asian market. Finisterra do Paço et al. (2009) stated that participants with the highest level of environmental concern were also those with the highest education levels. Similarly, higher-educated consumers were found to possess greater knowledge about green goods and the benefits of such products (Roslin et al., 2017). Also, research by Patak et al. (2021) showed that product knowledge is an antecedent of GPI. Many other studies reached similar conclusions regarding consumers' education levels (Dettmann & Dimitri, 2007; Magnusson et al., 2003; Zepeda & Li, 2007). Moreover, people with higher education levels demand more information on organic production methods and processes (Wier & Calverley, 2002). They are also more willing to pay more for organic food (Wandel & Bugge, 1997). Hence, the fourth hypothesis of this study is developed:

H4. There is a difference in green purchase intentions due to education level as a demographic factor.

3. METHODS

3.1. Participants and procedure

This study utilized quantitative research methods as they enable objective measurement of reality (Williams, 2007). A cross-sectional survey was used to collect the data among participants older than 18 living in Jordan, UAE, and KSA. Although this study applied a convenience sampling method, the aim was to collect a large sample to avoid biases associated with non-probability sampling (Sedgwick, 2013).

A digital version of the questionnaire was created using Google Forms and sent to the participants to collect responses conveniently. The survey was anonymous and required permission from the human subject. After collecting the responses, the data were cleaned and checked. The final sample included 680 useful responses.

3.2. Instrument design and measurement

The questionnaire consisted of two sections. The first section was created to collect demographic data from the participants. The country of residence was measured with three categories: Jordan, UAE, and KSA. Age was initially measured in years and then transformed into four age categories (OECD, 2022; new working lives – NWL – individuals aged 18 to 24, prime working lives – PWL – individuals aged 25 to 54, and peak passed working lives – PPWL – individuals aged 55 to 65). Additionally, a category of individuals aged 66 and over was added and categorized as retirement working lives (RWL). Gender was used as a nominal variable, including male and female. Education was measured on five levels: primary school (PS), high school (HS), bachelor's degree (BA), master's degree (MA), and doctorate degree (Ph.D.).

The second section was focused on collecting the data about GPI. Green purchase intentions were measured using the construct adopted from Paul et al. (2016), which was measured on a 7-point Likert scale ranging from very unlikely to very likely. As the original constructs were in English, a back translation (English-Arabic-English) was performed to ensure content validity.

3.3. Analysis

The data was analyzed using SPSS and AMOS software. Data analysis consisted of pretesting and testing of hypotheses. Pretesting included reliability, validity, and frequency analysis. Hypotheses were tested utilizing independent samples t-test and one-way ANOVA.

4. RESULTS

4.1. Pre-testing

Table 1 presents descriptive statistics, reliability, and validity for GPI.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics, reliability and validity for GPI

Variable	Item	SFL	M	SD	α	AVE	CR
GPI	GPI1	0.739	4.095	0.426	0.829	0.506	0.836
	GPI2	0.763					
	GPI3	0.636					
	GPI4	0.726					
	GPI5	0.686					

Note(s): M – mean; SD – standard deviation; SFL – standardized factor loadings; α – Cronbach’s alpha; AVE – average variance extracted; CR – composite reliability.

Source: Authors’ own.

Cronbach’s alpha is higher than 0.70, strongly indicating that the reliability of the construct has been reached (Cronbach, 1987). Furthermore, SFLs and AVE are above 0.5, while CR is higher than 0.60, which shows that convergent validity is also achieved.

Table 2: Frequency of responses per selected demographic variables

Variable	Category	N
Country	KSA	228
	UAE	209
	Jordan	243
Age	18-24	39
	25-54	581
	55-65	51
	66+	9
Gender	Male	403
	Female	277
Education	Primary school	3
	High school	47
	Undergraduate	513
	Masters	104
	Ph.D.	13

Note: N=680.

Source: Authors’ own.

Table 2 shows the frequency of responses per selected demographic variable. Regarding the country, 243 participants were from Jordan, 228 from the KSA, and 209 from the UAE. Regarding age, most participants (581) were between 25 and 54 years old. Additionally, 39 participants were 18-24 years old, while 51 participants belonged to the age category of 55-65 years, only 9 participants were

older than 66 years. Regarding gender, 403 participants were male, and 277 were female, meaning that the proportion of males in the sample was 68.74%. Regarding education level, 47 participants graduated from high school, most participants (513) held an undergraduate degree, 104 participants had a master's degree, and 13 participants held a Ph.D.

4.2. Hypotheses testing

A series of one-way ANOVA tests and independent samples t-tests were performed to test the hypotheses to check the interaction between demographic factors and GPI.

Table 3 and **Table 4** show GPI analyses based on the country of residence. **Table 3** shows the descriptive statistics of GPI based on country of residence. Results suggest that GPIs across countries are in the upper range of the scale. However, there is still much space for improvement. The highest mean (4.183) was reached by the KSA, indicating that respondents in this country have the highest intention to purchase green products. It is followed by UAE (4.067). Jordan scored the lowest mean (3.971).

Table 4 presents the results by comparing the mean differences for each country of residence. The results show no significant differences in GPI between Jordan and UAE and UAE and KSA. However, there is a significant difference between Jordan and KSA ($p = 0.030$). Such a result indicates that the **H1** is partially not supported.

Table 3: Descriptive statistics of GPI based on country of residence

Country	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Jordan	3.971	0.064	3.847	4.096
UAE	4.067	0.060	3.949	4.185
KSA	4.183	0.074	4.038	4.329

Source: Authors' own.

Table 4: Pairwise comparisons of GPI based on country of residence

Category 1 (C1)	Category 2 (C2)	Mean Difference (C1-C2)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval for Difference	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Jordan	UAE	-0.096	0.087	0.273	-0.268	0.076
Jordan	KSA	-0.212	0.098	0.030	-0.404	-0.020
UAE	KSA	-0.116	0.095	0.225	-0.303	0.072

Source: Authors' own.

Table 5: Descriptive statistics of GPI based on age category

Age category	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
NWL	3.956	0.083	3.794	4.118
PWL	4.065	0.046	3.975	4.155
PPWL	4.102	0.073	3.958	4.246
RWL	4.114	0.150	3.821	4.408

Source: Authors' own.

Table 6: Pairwise comparisons of GPI based on age category

Category 1 (C1)	Category 2 (C2)	Mean Difference (C1-C2)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval for Difference	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
NWL	PWL	-0.109	0.094	0.251	-0.294	0.077
NWL	PPWL	-0.145	0.110	0.188	-0.362	0.071
NWL	RWL	-0.158	0.171	0.355	-0.494	0.177
PWL	PPWL	-0.037	0.086	0.669	-0.207	0.133
PWL	RWL	-0.050	0.156	0.751	-0.357	0.258
PPWL	RWL	-0.013	0.167	0.940	-0.340	0.314

Source: Authors' own.

Table 7: Group Statistics and independent samples t-test - GPI based on gender

	N	M	SD	SE	t	df	Sig.
GPI							
Male	403	4.119	0.4167	0.0207	1.714	573.392	0.087
Female	277	4.061	0.4382	0.0263			

Source: Authors' own.

Table 8: Descriptive statistics of GPI based on education

Education	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
PS	4.200	0.240	3.728	4.672
HS	4.006	0.075	3.859	4.153
BA	4.036	0.048	3.942	4.130
MA	4.136	0.082	3.974	4.298
Ph.D.	4.187	0.144	3.904	4.470

Source: Authors' own.

Table 9: Pairwise comparisons of GPI based on education

Category 1 (C1)	Category 2 (C2)	Mean Difference (C1-C2)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval for Difference	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
PS	HS	.194 ^{a,b}	0.252	0.441	-0.300	0.688
PS	BA	.164 ^{a,b}	0.245	0.503	-0.317	0.645
PS	MA	.064 ^{a,b}	0.254	0.801	-0.435	0.563
PS	Ph.D.	.013 ^{a,b}	0.280	0.962	-0.537	0.563
HS	BA	-.030 ^{a,b}	0.089	0.736	-0.205	0.145
HS	MA	-.130 ^{a,b}	0.111	0.244	-0.349	0.089
HS	Ph.D.	-.181 ^{a,b}	0.162	0.266	-0.500	0.138
BA	MA	-.100 ^{a,b}	0.095	0.295	-0.287	0.087
BA	Ph.D.	-.151 ^{a,b}	0.152	0.321	-0.449	0.148
MA	Ph.D.	-.051 ^{a,b}	0.166	0.760	-0.377	0.275

Source: Authors' own.

Table 5 shows the descriptive statistics of GPI based on age category. As with the country of residence, GPI scores across different age groups are similar and in the upper range of the scale. However, the highest mean (4.114) was reached by RWL, indicating that respondents belonging to this group have the highest intention to purchase green products. Contrarily, respondents in the NWL age category scored the lowest mean (3.956). Generally, it seems that the GPI rises gradually with age categories. It should also be mentioned that RWL has the highest standard error, which can be attributed to the small number of respondents in this group (N=9).

Table 6 presents the results by comparing the mean differences for each age category. Results show that age does not play a significant role in GPI. Thus, **H2** is not supported.

Table 7 presents the statistical results and differences in gender regarding GPI. The means are in the upper range of the scale and relatively close regarding gender. However, the results of independent samples of the t-tests are conclusive that the difference in GPI between genders is not statistically significant. Therefore, **H3** is not supported.

Table 8 and **Table 9** show analyses of GPI based on education. Table 8 shows descriptive statistics for GPI based on education levels. Again, all educational levels' means are in the upper range of the scale and are close to each other. However, the PS category reached the highest mean (4.200), indicating that respondents in this group had the highest intention to purchase green products. Also, respondents in the Ph.D. category scored the second-highest mean with (4.187). Respondents from the HS category scored the lowest mean (4.006).

Table 9 compares the mean differences for each education level. However, the results are insignificant. Hence, **H4** is not supported.

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

Despite the recent increase in research on GPI, it is still a relatively new concept. However, the interest of researchers and marketers is not surprising, as studying GPI significantly contributes to understanding green consumer behavior. In line with this, the present study investigated the interplay between demographic factors such as country of residence, age, gender, and educational level and GPI in Jordan, UAE, and KSA.

The research question posed in this study was RQ1: What is the role of demographic factors (country of residence, age, gender, and education) in green purchase intention among consumers from KSA, Jordan, and UAE? Regarding the country of residence, many studies showed that Jordanian consumers are aware of green but still prefer traditional products (Al-Adamat & Al-adamat, 2019; Al-Adamat et al., 2020; Alsmadi, 2007; As' ad & Alhadid, 2014). For the UAE, studies demonstrated that consumers' awareness positively affected their intention to buy environmentally friendly products (Khaleeli et al., 2021). In the KSA, Groissböck et al. (2016) stated that the country faces serious environmental challenges, such as land degradation, desertification, and air pollution related to energy production. Government organizations are aware of these challenges. However, this study's results showed significant differences in GPI between Jordan and KSA, where respondents from Jordan achieved higher scores. Several explanations for such results are possible. One could be the higher income in KSA compared to Jordan, which can shift consumers' focus from price to other relevant aspects, such as sustainability. Another explanation could be government organizations' attitudes toward GPI in the KSA. These organizations provide the needed information and raise awareness about the importance of green products. Furthermore, the market's pricing policy and offering process could help consumers and traders.

Fisher et al. (2012) indicated that both younger and older people were likely to exhibit

environmentally friendly behaviors. Further, some studies emphasized the importance of age in GPI (e.g., Kim et al., 2012), while others found no connection between the two (e.g., Han et al., 2011). In line with the latter, this study's results suggest no significant differences in GPIs across different age groups. Although the differences are not statistically significant, younger respondents had lower GPI, which is in line with the assertion by Witek and Kuźniar (2020) that young people are skeptical about green products.

Regarding gender, the previous literature demonstrates an important area of investigation due to mixed conclusions from various studies. While many studies have indicated that female consumers showed higher interest in eco-friendly products (Fisher et al., 2012; Lee, 2009), evidence suggests that gender had no significant influence on GPI (Shahnaei, 2012). In line with the latter, this study's results suggest no significant difference in GPI between genders.

When it comes to education, most of the literature demonstrated that people with higher education levels require more information on organic production methods and processes and are more aware of green products (e.g., Finisterra do Paço et al., 2009; Roslin et al., 2017; Shahnaei, 2012). However, the results of this study oppose existing findings by showing no differences in GPI across different educational groups.

5.1. Implications of the results

The results provide findings that could be useful to companies interested in green consumer behavior. Therefore, this research carries several practical implications. Firstly, the results suggest no differences in GPI across Jordan, UAE, and KSA, except in comparison between Jordan and KSA. Companies can offer their green products using similar marketing strategies in these countries since all of them are characterized by similar levels of GPI. A first step for such businesses could be to open regional offices and support local suppliers and operators in handling ground services and operations. Next, services and coverage can be gradually developed and expanded based on consumers' feedback. Businesses can then customize the products according to the market. Additionally, businesses should focus on raising awareness and developing GPI in these countries, as there is much room for improvement.

Secondly, findings showed that age is not a relevant differentiator in GPI. Although insignificant, results show that GPI gradually increases with age. Therefore, companies should focus on all age groups when targeting them with green products. However, it is important to emphasize raising awareness of green consumption among younger generations that show somehow lower intention to purchase green products. Investments in this age category can pay off over the long run.

The study also showed that gender is not a significant differentiator in GPI. Therefore, companies should only use this demographic variable in their marketing strategy for green products if it is required due to good/service characteristics.

Finally, the study demonstrated no difference in GPI due to individual education levels. Therefore, companies should promote green consumption among members of all educational levels, as there is a lot of space for an increase in GPI.

5.2. Study limitations and future research

This study has limitations. Firstly, the study focused on differences in GPI based on demographic factors. Other studies could focus on predictors of these intentions, which would provide even more valuable theoretical and practical implications. Secondly, the study is based on data collected at one point and during the same period, limiting causal inferences and conclusions. Future studies could

therefore use a longitudinal study design to measure GPI at different time points and then make comparative assessments regarding demographic factors. Finally, the study deals with a multi-country sample, but these countries share many similar characteristics, such as culture, race, religion, and language. As demographic trends are one of the most dynamic in the current environment, future studies could investigate the scope of research in multicultural studies.

5.3. Conclusion

The aim of this study was to investigate the differences in GPI based on demographic factors in Jordan, UAE, and KSA. This study made four main contributions. First, the study enriches the existing literature on GPI by showing that certain differences in them could exist based on country of residence, even when countries share many similarities. Second, the study contributes to the literature on the interplay between age, gender, and education on one side and GPI on the other by showing that these demographic factors are not responsible for differences in intentions to purchase green products. Third, as explained earlier, these findings provide significant implications for companies operating relevant region.

Declarations

The authors have no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose. The data are available upon a reasonable request from the authors.

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Enhancing Financial Inclusion through Financial Literacy: Perceptions and Impact of Investment Deposits in Islamic Finance in Bosnia and Herzegovina

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ABSTRACT

This paper aims to examine the awareness and perceptions of depositors in Bosnia and Herzegovina regarding the features of investment deposits in Islamic finance. It evaluates the contribution of mudarabah-based deposits to the financial inclusion of Muslims and identifies factors influencing clients' decisions to place their funds in Islamic banks. The study employs a quantitative research methodology, utilizing an online survey distributed via LimeSurvey to collect primary data. The survey targeted bank clients in Bosnia and Herzegovina, and a non-random convenience sample was obtained by promoting the survey link on a Facebook page aimed at users in the region. Paid advertising was used to enhance visibility, and direct outreach was conducted in cities with Islamic bank branches to ensure a representative sample. The survey included questions on demographic information, awareness of investment deposits, understanding of Islamic finance, and attitudes towards banking risks and returns. The structured nature of the survey allowed for effective data collection and analysis to identify knowledge gaps and depositor attitudes. The findings reveal that a significant portion of respondents lack adequate knowledge about investment deposits, posing a critical barrier to their effective use for mobilizing savings and enhancing financial inclusion. Muslim clients identify interest as a significant hurdle to saving in conventional banks, with similar expectations and risk aversion observed in Islamic banking investment accounts. This research underscores the potential role of investment deposits in advancing financial inclusion by addressing knowledge gaps and examining factors influencing clients' decision-making processes. It highlights the need for increased awareness and education about investment deposits to facilitate their wider adoption among depositors, enhancing the understanding of leveraging Islamic finance principles to promote financial inclusion and meet the unique needs of Islamic savers and investors in Bosnia and Herzegovina.

ARTICLE HISTORY

Received: June 5, 2024

Accepted: June 10, 2024

Published: June 30, 2024

KEYWORDS

financial inclusion; deposits; investment deposits; mudarabah; Islamic finance; Bosnia and Herzegovina

JEL CODES

D12; E21; N35;

HOW TO CITE

Mešković, A., Aydin, Š., & Smolo, E. (2024). Enhancing Financial Inclusion through Financial Literacy: Perceptions and Impact of Investment Deposits in Islamic Finance in Bosnia and Herzegovina. *Journal of Economics, Law and Society*, 1(1), 39-53. <https://doi.org/10.70009/jels.2024.1.1.3>

1. INTRODUCTION

Financial inclusion, an important aspect of economic development, has garnered significant attention in recent years. It entails providing individuals with access to a wide range of affordable financial services, enabling them to save, invest, and participate actively in the formal financial system (Čihák et al., 2021). In many Muslim countries, promoting financial inclusion holds immense potential for fostering socio-economic growth and reducing disparities among its diverse population (Karlan et al., 2021).

Despite the recognized potential of financial inclusion to contribute to socio-economic growth,

especially in Muslim countries, there remains a significant gap in understanding and utilizing financial products aligned with Islamic principles, such as the *Mudarabah* model in investment deposits (Ahmed & Grais, 2014). This study aims to bridge this gap by exploring the role of these Islamic financial instruments in enhancing financial inclusion among Muslims in Bosnia and Herzegovina (B&H). It investigates depositors' knowledge and perceptions, and the factors influencing their decisions to engage with Islamic banks, specifically through investment deposits based on the *Mudarabah* model. The research seeks to address the barriers to financial inclusion posed by knowledge deficits, thereby contributing to broader economic development efforts in the region.

Investment deposits in Islamic finance are fundamentally different from the fixed-term deposits found in conventional banking (Cerović et al., 2017; Lee & Isa, 2019). These deposits are based on contracts grounded in Islamic finance principles, utilizing agreements such as *Qard*, *Wadiah*, and *Mudarabah* (Imady & Seibel, 2006). Specifically, Islamic banks operate on a profit-loss sharing system, where investment deposits are based on *Mudarabah* contracts, allowing customers to share in the profits and losses of the bank (Warninda, 2023).

Unlike conventional banking deposit agreements, these contracts introduce distinct differences in the nature of contractual risks, returns, or yields (Rammal, 2003).

However, there have been claims by practitioners and researchers in Islamic banking that the full implementation of investment deposit contracts is not always upheld in practice (Khan et al., 2021). Both Islamic banks' adherence to the contractual terms and depositors' perception of the possibility of realizing the risk of partial loss of principal have come under scrutiny. Depositors often expect Islamic banks to cover potential losses, despite Islamic economic principles stating that such compensation is infeasible for this deposit type. This expectation may stem from a lack of knowledge or misconceptions about Islamic banking, heavily influenced by conventional banking norms, or from the regulatory framework that affects Islamic banking's implementation in a specific country. Thus, the primary objective of this research is to investigate the level of knowledge and perception among depositors in B&H regarding the characteristics of investment deposits as outlined in Islamic finance theory. Furthermore, the study aims to explore the practical applicability of these deposit types from both a regulatory perspective and the acceptance by clients.

The results of this investigation will present essential insights for policymakers, financial institutions, and stakeholders focused on enhancing financial inclusion in B&H. They will emphasize the vital importance of investment deposits in bridging the gap between conventional and Islamic banking. This article advocates for a financial ecosystem that meets the diverse needs of the population. Supported by empirical research, this approach outlines a path toward a more inclusive financial system that could greatly aid in wider socio-economic development (Ozili, 2022).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Financial inclusion, defined as providing individuals with access to a range of affordable financial services (Dev, 2006), is a critical aspect of socio-economic development. Islamic finance operates on the principles of equity, risk-sharing, and ethical investment, providing a unique framework for financial transactions aligned with Shariah principles (Hassan & Kayed, 2009). Studies made by authors such as Shinkafi et al. (2020), Baber (2020), Siddiqui et al. (2021) have highlighted the potential of Islamic finance to enhance financial inclusion by catering to the specific needs and religious beliefs of Muslim individuals. Islamic financial instruments, such as profit-sharing agreements (*Mudarabah*), joint ventures (*Musharakah*), and Islamic microfinance, have been examined as effective tools for expanding financial access to underserved Muslim populations.

When exploring the determinants of Islamic financial inclusion in Indonesia, Ali et al. (2020)

revealed that both supply and demand factors significantly influence Islamic financial inclusion. Key demand factors identified include financial literacy, religious commitment, socioeconomic factors, and social influence. On the supply side, critical factors are human capital, product and service offerings, infrastructure, and policies and regulations. Most of the literature on the financial inclusion and Islamic finance actually revolves around these factors.

The most prominent supply factor in the literature on Islamic finance inclusion is the existence of the necessary infrastructure (Wilson, 2000; Kamer et al., 2015). More specifically, the studies have highlighted the importance of establishing Islamic banking institutions and the role of regulations and policies in facilitating their growth (Johnson, 2013). Factors such as geographical availability and proximity to Islamic banking branches have been identified as crucial determinants of access to Islamic financial services (Chowdhury & Rasid, 2016). Further, Shinkafi et al. (2020) review research on factors promoting financial inclusion in Islamic finance, highlighting key drivers for inclusion among women, low-income earners, and the rural poor. According to them, these include advanced technology, microcredit and microfinance services, legal and regulatory frameworks, and infrastructure. They conclude their study by highlighting that a broad framework integrating technology, political commitment, financial access, and awareness is vital for achieving financial inclusion in the Muslim world.

However, infrastructure alone does not guarantee increased use of Islamic banking services. Specifically, financial literacy is one of the most important drivers of financial inclusion (Smolo et al., 2022). Islamic financial literacy emerges as the most significant demand factor affecting Islamic financial inclusion. Even Shinkafi et al. (2020), who heavily emphasized the role of supply factors in promoting Islamic financial inclusion, acknowledged the importance of demand factors like public awareness of Islamic finance and Islamic financial literacy. The study by Albaity and Rahman (2019) assesses Islamic financial literacy and its impact—along with awareness, reputation, and attitudes towards Islamic banking—on the intention to use Islamic banking. Interestingly, while cost and benefit factors were not found to significantly affect intention, Islamic financial literacy, awareness, reputation, and attitude did. Initially, Islamic financial literacy showed a negative correlation with usage intention, but this turned positive when mediated by attitudes towards Islamic banking. The findings underline the critical role of enhancing Islamic financial knowledge and fostering positive attitudes towards Islamic banks to boost usage intention.

The role of Islamic financial literacy in general and Islamic financial knowledge in specific is the evident in some other studies as well. However, the customer behavior in Islamic banking is a relatively underexplored area, with one of the first studies published in 1989 by Erol and El-Bdour, focusing on “Attitudes, Behavior, and Patronage Factors of Bank Customers towards Islamic Banks.” Another early study in Malaysia by Haron et al. in 1994 echoed similar findings. These initial investigations revealed that although customers are aware of Islamic banks and their distinct products, their knowledge remains limited. This gap in understanding is identified as a primary barrier preventing wider adoption of Islamic banking services. Further research by Hamid and Nordin (2001) in Kuala Lumpur, involving both conventional and Islamic bank clients, supported these findings. More recently, Haque et al. (2009) confirmed that the situation regarding clients’ knowledge of Islamic banking products in Malaysia has seen little improvement. This consistent theme highlights the crucial need for enhanced educational efforts to bridge the knowledge gap and foster greater engagement with Islamic banking.

The importance of knowledge of Islamic banking is evident in the results of studies from other countries too. For instance, Metawa and Almosawi (1998) focused on Bahrain, Bley and Kuehn (2004) on the UAE, and Naser et al. (1999) on Jordan. Namely, these studies reveal that clients in the Middle East generally understand basic banking products like savings or current accounts and ATMs. However, they show less familiarity with complex Islamic finance models such as Mudarabah and

Musharaka, leading to less frequent use. Additionally, the studies highlight that the use of Arabic financial terminology can confuse clients. Unsurprisingly, native Arabic speakers tend to have a better grasp of Islamic banking concepts, suggesting a language barrier impacts understanding of these financial models.

Some studies revealed the importance of non-financial factors in Islamic financial inclusion. For example, in their study, Haron and Shanmugam (1995) discovered that BIMB Islamic bank depositors did not prioritize profit rates when deciding where to place their deposits. Surprisingly, they found an inverse relationship between profit rates on deposits and the levels of deposits, contradicting typical depositor behavior. A more recent investigation by Mohd Karim (2010) further examined attitudes towards Islamic deposits. These studies collectively suggest that clients choose certain Islamic banking products for religious reasons, rather than for expected profits. Additionally, a study by the State Bank of Pakistan (Durrani, 2016) showed that 62 percent of surveyed individuals were willing to pay more for Sharia-compliant banking products. Meanwhile, 36 percent stated they would not withdraw their investment if the bank reported negative returns, highlighting the significance of Sharia compliance over financial returns among Pakistani banking clients.

Similarly, article by Karlan et al. (2021) studies the preference for Sharia-compliant loans over conventional loans in a Muslim-majority country, finding a stronger demand and a higher willingness to pay for sharia-compliant products despite their financial similarities to conventional options. The study reveals that the authorizing entity has little effect on the demand for these loans, but price sensitivity varies with religiosity, as shown by viewership of religious TV. It suggests that survey data may overstate the exclusionary influence of religious goals, underlining the role of religious and social factors in credit decisions. The findings highlight the potential for financial inclusion by acknowledging non-financial preferences in financial decision-making. Products designed to meet these preferences, even at a higher cost, can attract individuals valuing these features, thus expanding access to formal financial services for those who might avoid them for social or religious reasons. This approach can make it economically viable to offer such products and integrate more people into the formal financial system.

The literature has identified various challenges and opportunities in the realm of financial inclusion through Islamic finance. Challenges encompass limited access to Islamic financial services, the absence of standardized Shariah-compliant products, and inadequate regulatory frameworks (Čihák & Hesse, 2010). Cultural and social factors, gender disparities, and technological barriers also pose significant impediments to financial inclusion (Warde, 2010; Kammer et al., 2015). Conversely, opportunities exist in utilizing technology for digital Islamic finance solutions, enhancing partnerships between Islamic financial institutions and conventional banks, and promoting financial education and awareness (Dusuki & Abdullah, 2007; Iqbal & Molyneux, 2016).

3. POSSIBILITIES OF INVESTMENT ACCOUNTS IMPLEMENTATION IN CONVENTIONAL REGULATORY ENVIRONMENT IN EUROPE

Implementing investment deposit models in B&H can be explored and achieved through several approaches, which include regulatory framework, awareness and education, technology, and partnerships.

For successful implementation of investment deposits, regulatory bodies should consider adapting regulations and creating an appropriate framework that supports this type of banking product. This includes establishing rules for the formation and management of investment deposits, as well as ensuring the protection of investor interests. Banking institutions can invest efforts in educating clients about investment deposits and their benefits. This may involve organizing seminars,

workshops, and campaigns to enhance awareness about the potential advantages and risks associated with such products.

Banks can establish partnerships with investment institutions to leverage their knowledge and expertise in investment management. This can enable access to a wide range of investment opportunities and portfolio diversification for investment deposits. Banking institutions can leverage advanced technologies such as digital platforms and process automation to facilitate the opening and management of investment deposits. This can improve the user experience and provide faster and more efficient services to investors. Collaborating with international institutions such as international banks or investment funds can provide additional support and knowledge regarding the implementation of investment deposits. These partnerships can open new opportunities for investors and grant access to global markets.

Deposit insurance is the first characteristic of the domestic banking system that we will analyze in the context of investment deposit based on Mudarabah. According to Article 14 of the Law on Banks of the Federation of B&H (2017), „All banks to which the Agency has granted a banking license shall be obliged to fulfill the membership conditions for deposit insurance in order to retain their license.“ Furthermore, Article 17 of the same law states that a bank will lose its operating license in case of non-compliance with the membership conditions in the deposit insurance system. It is clear, therefore, that investment deposits must be insured, which is not in line with the principle of Mudarabah, where the investment risk is assumed by the capital owner. This regulatory barrier can be partially overcome by informing the client that, according to Shariah, they are not allowed to withdraw the entire deposit amount in case of lower returns or losses. This is the stance of the Shariah Board of BBI Bank.

One of the major regulatory barriers for implementing deposit contracts based on Mudarabah is the Decision on the Uniform Method of Calculation and Disclosure of the Effective Interest Rate on Loans and Deposits, issued by the Federal Banking Agency in May 2012. This decision prescribes a unified method of calculation and disclosure of the effective interest rate on loans provided by banks and microcredit organizations, as well as the effective interest rate on deposits held with banks. According to this decision, the bank must inform clients of the effective interest rate before accepting a deposit request and before concluding a deposit agreement. When entering into a deposit agreement, the bank must provide the client with a copy of the repayment plan, clearly indicating the effective interest rate, which is considered an integral part of the agreement. If the effective interest rate changes due to changes in the calculation elements, the bank is required to notify the client in writing of such changes before the revised effective interest rate takes effect. In the case of variable interest rates, the bank must clearly define the conditions for changing the rate in the agreement.

Furthermore, the Law on the Protection of Financial Services Users (2014) stipulates in Article 21 that a deposit agreement must include, among other things:

4) the amount of the nominal annual interest rate, with an indication of whether the user is obliged to pay taxes;

the effective interest rate and the total amount to be paid to the user, calculated on the day of concluding the agreement;

the amount of the insured monetary deposit.

Regarding variable rates, only officially published elements such as the reference interest rate or the consumer price index can be considered variable elements. The return on a specific investment pool cannot be considered an officially published element, and therefore, it cannot determine the

return on deposits with variable rates. Moreover, even if it were possible, the law states that the bank must inform the user in written or electronic form about any changes in the rate before the revised rate takes effect. With investment deposits, it is not possible to apply any predetermined rate of return; the return is determined subsequently.

Similar legal solutions are prescribed in the Law on Banks of the Republika Srpska in Article 98, which requires that the deposit agreement indicate the nominal and effective interest rates, as well as the total amount to be paid to the user upon maturity.

Based on all the aforementioned, we can conclude that the first hypothesis, which states, “It is possible to apply deposit contracts based on profit sharing from investment in B&H,” is rejected. Due to certain provisions of the laws of the Government of the Federation of B&H and the sublegal acts of the Banking Agency of the Federation of B&H, which primarily aim to protect clients, it is not possible to implement deposit contracts based on profit sharing from investment of deposit funds.

These legal barriers and regulations pose significant challenges to the implementation of investment deposit models based on Mudarabah in B&H. They require deposit insurance, standardized calculation and disclosure of interest rates, and specific provisions in deposit agreements that may not align with the principles of Mudarabah. As a result, the application of such deposit contracts is currently not feasible within the existing legal framework.

It is important to note that these regulatory barriers can be overcome through amendments to the relevant laws and regulations or the introduction of specific provisions that accommodate the principles of Mudarabah and enable the implementation of investment deposit models in accordance with Islamic finance principles. However, such changes would require a comprehensive review and adjustment of the legal framework governing banking and financial services in B&H.

Therefore, while the potential for implementing investment deposit models based on Mudarabah exists in theory, the current regulatory landscape in B&H presents significant challenges and limitations. Any future progress in this regard would require a comprehensive and coordinated effort involving regulatory authorities, Islamic financial institutions, and relevant stakeholders to create a conducive legal and regulatory environment for the implementation of investment deposit contracts based on profit sharing.

Furthermore, there are several open questions that need to be addressed before the implementation of this type of deposit. Some of the areas to consider include:

- Defining the accounting treatment for recording each individual fund (which accounts to use for these funds, how to record the return of principal and profit)
- Defining the accounting treatment for reserves (PER and IRR)
- Defining the accounting treatment for recording gross profit
- Defining the accounting treatment for direct costs related to mudaraba investments (costs deducted from gross profit)
- Defining the accounting treatment or accounts for recording allocated or net profit (profit sharing between the client and the bank)
- Defining the accounting treatment for realized losses from a project and how to record them based on individual client investments
- Defining the accounting treatment for placements from sources based on mudaraba
- Defining the accounting treatment for returns from such placements (principal

and profit)

- Defining the accounting treatment for provisions related to these placements (provision costs should belong to mudaraba investors according to the mudaraba model)
- Defining the accounting treatment in case a placement becomes non-performing (this cost should be passed on to the investors according to the mudaraba agreement)
- Defining the accounting treatment in case of collecting disputed receivables (these receivables should also belong to the investors)

In addition to the accounting treatment, it is necessary to define how PER and IRR reserves could function, the stance of the Federal Banking Agency on the fact that the expected return is not guaranteed in these deposits, as well as the procedure in case of loss and the procedure in case the bank collects the return subsequently (e.g., through legal action). Managing various types of risks, both “conventional” and specific to this type of product, is also an open question.

Regarding future research, Article 39 of the Law on Banks of the Federation of B&H specifies the activities that a bank can carry out in the territory of the Federation of B&H. Among other things, a bank can accept all types of monetary deposits and engage in financial management services. An issue for future research is whether a bank’s activities with investment accounts can be categorized as financial management rather than deposit-taking activities. The role of the bank in investment accounts is closer to financial management than deposit-taking activities.

In this chapter, we have examined the possibilities of implementing investment accounts in the practice of Islamic banks in B&H, taking into account the legal regulations and other conditions. In the next chapter, we will explore the market for such products, specifically the perspective of potential depositors.

4. EXAMINING CLIENT PERCEPTION

A significant number of both published and unpublished (intended only for internal use) research studies focus on conventional banking, with a considerable portion analyzing clients’ motives for selecting a banking service provider. This study blends exploratory and descriptive research approaches. In the exploratory phase, we aim to explore depositors’ perceptions of the unique characteristics of investment deposit accounts. Descriptively, this study aims to enrich the existing literature in the field.

4.1. Methodology

In this research, we employ a quantitative approach using survey methods to test auxiliary hypotheses. The questionnaire was distributed via LimeSurvey, an online platform. We analyzed primary data collected from the survey to understand Islamic bank clients’ perceptions of investment deposit accounts and their features. Primary data is deemed ideal for this type of research as it provides direct insights from the target population (Groves et al., 2009). The hypotheses tested in this study include:

- The majority of bank clients in B&H are not sufficiently familiar with the concept of investment deposits in Islamic banking.
- The majority of bank clients in B&H expect the bank to provide the same returns regardless of the bank’s business performance.
- The majority of bank clients in B&H are willing to accept higher risk in investment deposits in exchange for the potential of higher returns compared to the existing returns

achievable with fixed deposits.

The structured nature of surveys allows for direct data collection from a broad audience, aligning with our exploratory and descriptive objectives to identify knowledge gaps and depositor attitudes effectively (Fowler, 2014). The survey was designed to directly align with our research objectives, consisting of structured questions across several sections. Initially, it gathers demographic information to segment analysis by relevant variables (age, income, banking history). Following sections delve into respondents' awareness of investment deposits, understanding of Islamic finance, and attitudes towards banking risks and returns. Questions mix multiple-choice for straightforward topics and Likert scales for nuanced issues, crafted to be clear and accessible to those unfamiliar with banking terminologies (Likert, 1932).

The survey consists of six main questions, two of which have additional sub-questions. The questions are divided into two groups. The first group of questions explores socio-demographic information about the respondents, as well as their knowledge level regarding investment deposits. The second group of questions analyzes the respondents' attitudes towards the unique characteristics of investment accounts. All questions are closed-ended with multiple-choice options, while the last two questions are created in the form of a Likert scale ranging from 1 to 5 (being strongly disagree and strongly agree). According to DeVellis (2016) such question format is preferable both in terms of response rate, as they are easier to answer, and in terms of analyzing the obtained responses.

4.2. Sample

In this research, the target population comprises bank clients in B&H. A bank client is defined as any individual who holds an account with any bank, regardless of the type of account. Due to the unfeasibility of surveying the entire population, a non-random convenience sample was selected as a representative subset. The sample was obtained by strategically promoting the survey link, along with accompanying messages, on a Facebook page specifically targeted at users in B&H. Paid advertising on Facebook was utilized to increase the visibility of the survey among the target audience.

Facebook was selected for sample recruitment due to its wide reach and advanced targeting features, allowing us to engage a diverse demographic likely to have banking experience. Targeting was based on location, age, and interests related to finance and banking. To mitigate potential online sampling biases (e.g., over-representation of tech-savvy individuals), we also targeted specific regions with Islamic bank branches and conducted direct outreach to ensure a broader sample.

To ensure the inclusion of an adequate number of respondents who are clients of Islamic banks, additional efforts were made. Specifically, cities where BBI Bank operates its branches were targeted to capture a representative sample of Islamic banking clients. Furthermore, direct outreach was conducted to individuals who were assumed to be potential users of Islamic banking services, thereby diversifying the sample.

Considering the nature of a non-probabilistic sample, the determination of the sample size took into account both practical considerations and the cost-benefit ratio. The aim was to strike a balance between obtaining a sufficient number of responses and optimizing available resources.

Ultimately, a total of 444 respondents engaged in the process of completing the survey. The overall sample size can be considered adequate for the purposes of analysis and drawing meaningful conclusions.

4.3. Results and analysis

In the analysis of the survey results, we will focus on the responses provided by the participants, particularly on several questions that test specific hypotheses. Regarding the composition of the respondents, 23% of them are clients of Islamic bank, while two-thirds are clients of other banks, with 8.8% of the respondents not providing a response to this question. The majority of respondents (53.16%) have only a current account, while 15.79% have a savings account, and 5.79% have a fixed-term deposit account at a bank. The largest proportion of respondents (39%) have monthly incomes below 1,000 KM, and the percentage of respondents decreases with increasing income levels.

Regarding the first hypothesis tested, the survey results indicate that the majority of respondents indeed have insufficient knowledge about investment deposits, thereby confirming the hypothesis. Additional questions further support the finding of a general lack of awareness regarding investment deposits. This outcome is anticipated, given the limited availability of this product in B&H and the lack of active education efforts by the local Islamic bank on investment deposits. Nonetheless, Islamic bank clients showed significantly greater knowledge of this product than those of conventional banks. This suggests that Islamic bank clients likely gained familiarity with investment deposits through their education, information from friends or bank staff, or the printed materials distributed by BBI Bank to promote Islamic banking.

The next hypothesis, which explores whether clients would be willing to accept higher risk in investment deposits for the potential of higher returns, is partially confirmed. It is important to note that the median response is “Partially agree,” not “Completely agree.” This indicates that while clients are open to a higher risk level, there is a limit to this willingness. Additionally, Islamic bank clients show a greater readiness to embrace this risk, likely due to the perception that investment deposits align better with the Islamic economy compared to other deposit types. However, the majority of respondents believe that the Islamic bank should absorb any losses that occur. Differences emerge between clients of Islamic and conventional banks: those from conventional banks tend to believe the bank should bear the loss, whereas Islamic bank clients, more cognizant of Sharia principles in the *mudarabah* contract, show a greater willingness to accept the loss themselves.

The majority of respondents expressed a desire to diversify their savings by allocating some of their funds to investment deposits. However, over two-thirds expect the bank to avoid excessively risky investments with the funds from these deposits. Therefore, whether this hypothesis is definitively confirmed depends on the specific level of risk and the expected returns achievable.

Regarding the hypothesis related to the expectation of constant returns, most clients still prioritize consistent returns on their deposits, independent of the bank’s investment performance. The data shows that a significant number of clients prefer predictable rates of return on their investments. Yet, a considerable group of respondents does not align with this perspective, showing openness to variable returns based on different situations. This is underscored by responses to whether clients would accept the bank setting aside profits to cover future losses, with the majority in favor, supporting the hypothesis of constant and predictable returns. Further evidence for this hypothesis comes from inquiries about withdrawal behaviors in response to lower-than-expected returns. Over half of the clients (52%) indicated they would withdraw their deposits under such circumstances, whereas 37% would not. Additionally, in scenarios of realized Sharia risk, over 70% of respondents would withdraw their deposits. About 65% of respondents would hesitate to deposit if the principal amount lacked deposit insurance. Moreover, nearly all clients expressed a desire for transparency regarding the utilization of investment deposit funds and requested detailed explanations of the Sharia aspects of the investment deposit agreement from bank representatives.

In summary, the survey results offer valuable insights into respondents’ awareness and preferences

concerning investment deposits. The data reveal a general lack of knowledge and understanding of this financial product among most participants. Nonetheless, Islamic bank clients demonstrate a greater familiarity with investment deposits, likely attributed to prior exposure through educational efforts or bank interactions. Attitudes towards accepting higher risks for the potential of higher returns also differ, with Islamic bank clients displaying a greater openness to risk. Furthermore, while a significant number of clients show a preference for stable and predictable returns, opinions on this matter vary. The findings illuminate the perceptions and expectations clients hold towards investment deposits, presenting essential information for Islamic and conventional banks in B&H.

5. IMPLICATIONS

The results of this study on depositor perceptions and knowledge regarding Islamic banking investment deposits in B&H have important implications for policymakers, financial institutions, and stakeholders focused on improving financial inclusion. By uncovering depositor attitudes towards Islamic banking, especially investment deposits, the study highlights a significant knowledge gap. Addressing this gap could markedly influence the landscape of financial inclusion.

For policymakers, the study emphasizes the need to create regulatory frameworks and educational initiatives tailored to the distinct features of Islamic banking. Enhancing public comprehension of Islamic finance principles can demystify investment deposits, promoting broader engagement with the banking system.

Financial institutions, particularly those providing Islamic banking services, can utilize these findings to refine their product offerings and marketing approaches, aligning more closely with the needs and expectations of prospective depositors. This entails developing clearer and more accessible informational resources that elucidate the principles and advantages of investment deposits, thereby bridging the knowledge gap highlighted in the study.

The study underscores the potential appeal of Islamic banking to depositors seeking alternatives to conventional banking, motivated by religious or ethical considerations. Financial institutions could develop innovative products that resonate with these preferences, ensuring competitive returns and security. This approach addresses the financial and ethical considerations of potential clients.

Additionally, the findings indicate a willingness among certain population segments to embrace the higher risks of investment deposits for the chance of higher returns. This reveals a market opportunity for Islamic banks to create and offer investment products that accommodate different risk tolerances, all while staying true to principles of Islamic finance.

6. CONCLUSION

This research on the role of investment deposits in Islamic banking and their potential to boost financial inclusion in B&H reveals several key insights. Investment deposits, based on the mudarabah principle, offer a unique avenue for individuals with excess funds to participate in profit-sharing endeavors with Islamic banks. In this arrangement, the bank acts as the mudarib (manager), and the depositor provides capital, forming a partnership where both returns and risks are shared, without guarantees on the principal or returns.

Our analysis of the adoption and perception of these deposits in B&H has produced complex results. Contrary to the hypothesis that the profit-sharing model of Islamic banking would fit easily into the B&H financial environment, we encountered significant legal and regulatory barriers. The requirement for banks to provide fixed return rates upfront clashes with the inherent uncertainty of mudarabah contracts, highlighting a critical mismatch. This conflict indicates the need for

regulatory reform, perhaps looking towards models like the ones in Malaysia. There, investment accounts are differentiated from standard deposit contracts, more closely resembling financial management practices than traditional deposit-taking, suggesting a pathway for integration into B&H's financial system.

Survey responses from 444 bank clients in B&H further illuminate the current state of awareness and attitudes towards Islamic banking's investment deposits:

- i. A substantial segment of the population is unfamiliar with investment deposits, likely attributed to the absence of these products in the local market. This gap highlights the urgent need for educational efforts to bridge the knowledge divide.
- ii. There is a prevalent expectation among respondents for stable returns from banking investments, mirroring practices in other regions where Islamic banks maintain reserves to stabilize depositor returns. This finding highlights a fundamental tension between the expectations of depositors and the risk-sharing principles of Islamic finance.
- iii. Despite this, there is a noticeable willingness among respondents to accept higher risks for potentially greater returns, suggesting a nuanced comprehension and acceptance of the risk-reward balance inherent in *mudarabah* contracts. Yet, this acceptance is moderated by a desire for a certain level of return predictability.
- iv. The variation in responses between clients of Islamic banks and those of conventional banks illustrates the diversity in financial landscapes and depositor expectations within B&H. These insights challenge traditional views on the compatibility of Islamic banking with the B&H financial system and shed light on both the opportunities and obstacles for its deeper integration and acceptance.

This study establishes a foundation for a wider dialogue on the contribution of Islamic finance to financial inclusion. It urges a collaborative approach among policymakers, regulators, and Islamic financial institutions to overcome legal hurdles, improve public comprehension of Islamic finance principles, and develop financial products that align with depositor expectations under Islamic banking principles. Future research should explore the socio-economic implications of incorporating Islamic finance more fully into B&H and Herzegovina's financial system, examining the potential benefits and challenges that accompany such integration.

7. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

This study provides important insights into depositor perceptions and knowledge regarding Islamic banking's investment deposits in B&H. However, it faces several limitations that highlight areas for future research. The use of an online survey distributed via Facebook may not fully represent the broader population's views, particularly those less engaged with digital platforms. The reliance on self-reported data risks social desirability bias, potentially skewing the accuracy of depositor behaviors and perceptions. Additionally, the study's cross-sectional design captures attitudes at a specific point in time without accounting for dynamic changes in the financial landscape or depositor perspectives.

Future research could benefit from a mixed-methods approach, integrating qualitative interviews or focus groups to delve deeper into the motivations behind depositor attitudes towards Islamic banking. Longitudinal studies would offer valuable insights into how these attitudes evolve over time in response to changing market conditions and regulatory environments. Expanding the geographic scope of the research and targeting non-users of banking services would enhance understanding of the factors influencing the adoption of Islamic banking products. Moreover, assessing the impact of Islamic banking on depositor financial health and community economic development

could provide concrete evidence of its benefits and limitations for financial inclusion.

Declarations

The authors have no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose. The data are available upon a reasonable request from the corresponding author.

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The Rise of Green Bonds: Global Context and European Insights

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ABSTRACT

This paper analyzes the global and European green bond markets from different perspectives. The paper uses data on green bond issues in the global and European green bond markets from 2013 to 2023. Research results show that the issuance of green and other sustainability-related revenue use bonds has increased in recent years. Europe remains the largest issuance region, accounting for over half of global issuance. Green bond issuance globally and in Europe has experienced a tumultuous couple of years after reaching record highs of USD 575 billion and USD 326 billion in 2021, respectively. In 2023, Europe's green bond issuance recovered 11% year on year to USD 341 billion. It slightly outperformed the global markets, which recorded 10% growth to reach USD 581 billion. In line with 2022, the corporate sector fueled 2023 green volume, contributing 57% of issuance. Corporate issuers in Europe are dominated mainly by the energy, utilities, automotive, transport, and building sectors, all of which have historically been dependent on fossil fuels. Analysis of the capital markets in Bosnia and Herzegovina (BiH) indicates that the green bond market exists, and it started in 2023 when the first issue of green bonds was announced by a commercial bank on the local capital market (Banja Luka Stock Exchange). The critical barriers to developing the green bond market are the lack of appropriate institutional arrangements for green bond management, the issue of minimum size, and the high transaction costs associated with issuing green bonds.

ARTICLE HISTORY

Received: June 10, 2024

Accepted: June 18, 2024

Published: June 30, 2024

KEYWORDS

green bonds; green financing; green bond market; barriers to the development of green bonds; BiH; ESG

JEL CODES

E44; G10; O13; Q40; Q56;

HOW TO CITE

Ibrić, M., Kozarević, E. & Mešković, A. (2024). The Rise of Green Bonds: Global Context and European Insights. *Journal of Economics, Law and Society*, 1(1), 55-71. <https://doi.org/10.70009/jels.2024.1.1.4>

1. INTRODUCTION

The EU's commitment to the objectives of the Paris Agreement and the ambitious European Green Deal requires significant investment (Kozarević & Ibrić, 2023). One of the major issues is how to finance the transition to a global low-carbon economy. Hodžić et al. (2023) suggest that green finance, or green financing, can be seen as the financing of investments that yield environmental benefits, such as reducing air, water, and soil pollution, lowering greenhouse gas emissions, enhancing energy efficiency, and mitigating and adapting to climate change. Without a global carbon pricing scheme, bond markets become central to financing these interventions (Teti et al., 2022). Green bonds – fixed-income securities explicitly designed to support climate and environmental projects – are an essential instrument of green finance. However, while the green bond market is growing rapidly, it is younger and relatively small compared to the overall bond market. Green bonds are one of the main instruments regulators and markets are considering to green the economy and the financial sector (EPRS, 2022). Regulations play a crucial role in the development of environmentally

or socially responsible instruments (Meskovic et al., 2023). As pointed out by the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2017), with banks having restricted lending capabilities and public budgets under strain in many countries, private sector sources of capital need to be engaged and so, green bonds are considered among the key instruments to mobilize private financial resources towards the progressive decarbonization of the global economy. Green bonds explicitly create a flow of funds toward projects that offer environmental benefits by combining the efforts of issuers and investors. They are expected to become a pathway by which financial market participants can fulfill their primary responsibilities toward maintaining a sustainable global environment while simultaneously pursuing investment opportunities (Santiago, 2020). Globally, the number of green bonds issued has risen explosively (Sobik, 2023).

The green bond market has experienced significant growth since its inception in 2007. By 2017, it had expanded to nearly USD 900 billion, illustrating its increasing importance in financing environmentally sustainable projects (Pawłowski, 2018). Despite this growth, the market remains relatively small compared to the challenges it aims to address and the broader traditional bond market. Significant barriers include the lack of harmonized global standards, risks of greenwashing, and perceptions of higher costs for issuers (Deschryver & de Mariz, 2020).

When examining the literature that analyzes this area (e.g., Agliardi & Agliardi, 2019; Bachelet et al., 2019; Hachenberg & Schiereck, 2018; Chiang, 2017; Flaherty et al., 2017; Moldashbayeva et al., 2021; Banga, 2018; Gianfrate & Peri, 2019; Wang & Zhi, 2016; Glomsrød & Wei, 2018; Kochetygova et al., 2016), it can be noticed that there is a research gap related to conditions influencing the development of the European green bonds market.

In emerging markets, the interest in green bonds is growing, supported by favorable market reactions on the day of issuance (Sreelakshmi & Greeshma, 2023). However, the rapid issuance of green bonds does not necessarily indicate that bond markets are becoming greener. Challenges such as weak governance frameworks limit their contribution to sustainable development (Berensmann et al., 2018).

Additionally, there is a research gap in the literature investigating the green bond market in Bosnia and Herzegovina (BiH). To fill the gap in the existing literature, this paper aims to provide a comprehensive study related to the development and barriers to the green bonds market in Europe, with a particular focus on BiH. The selection of BiH is not coincidental; it is a country facing the need for a profound decarbonization of the economy and a comprehensive energy transition.

The green bond market is gradually gaining traction in developing countries, including Bosnia and Herzegovina. This growth is driven by the need to finance sustainable development goals and environmental projects. In Bosnia and Herzegovina, as in some other developing nations, the introduction of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) principles is in its early stages. However, there is increasing awareness of their importance in attracting global investors and supporting sustainable finance.

The green bond market in developing countries faces several challenges. Key barriers include the lack of appropriate institutional frameworks, high transaction costs, and issues related to the minimum size of issuances (Banga, 2018). Despite these challenges, there are significant opportunities for growth.

Empirical studies have shown that promoting green bonds in developing countries can significantly reduce CO₂ emissions and support environmentally friendly projects, thereby contributing to the fight against global warming (Arshad et al., 2024). Furthermore, introducing ESG principles has been shown to positively impact firm performance in developing countries, such as those in the

ASEAN region, highlighting the potential benefits of integrating ESG criteria into financial markets (Makhdalena et al., 2023).

The following text gives an insight into the research questions that our research paper tries to answer and the research aim and objectives.

Research Question: Are there significant differences in the European green bond market structure compared to the global green bond market?

Research Aim: Global and European green bonds market analysis from different perspectives.

Research Objectives:

RQ1: Analyze and compare global and European green bond markets: This includes examining the share of the global green bond market in the total GSS+ market, comparing the value of green bond issues globally and in Europe, and analyzing the European green bond market by type of issuer and use of proceeds.

RQ2: Examine the green bond market in Bosnia and Herzegovina (BiH): This involves analyzing the emerging green bond market in BiH, identifying barriers to its development, and evaluating the significance of its growth.

Propose measures for improvement: Systematize strategies and measures to enhance the development and efficiency of the green bond market, focusing on overcoming identified barriers.

The paper is structured as follows. Section 1 provides an insight into the context of the research. Section 2 presents the data and the methodology. Section 3 illustrates the output and discusses its results. Section 4 concludes and suggests future research that could complement the present work, further developing the green bonds literature.

2. BACKGROUND

The financial system is crucial to support and accelerate investment for sustainable development and decarbonizing the economy. However, the successful development of the green financial system also requires the existence of economic motives of investors (Santiago, 2020). It is not straightforward for investors to decide to invest in green projects. While, due to innovation, the cost of cleaner technologies has fallen in recent years, investors still perceive many environmentally or society-friendly projects as risky. In 2017, Schwerhoff and Sy suggested that the bulk of large-scale renewable projects must be supported through debt financing (Santiago, 2020). One of the forms of raising capital through debt is the issue of green bonds.

Europe is at the forefront of green bond issuance. Global green bond issuance started with multi-lateral development banks (MDBs) raising funding for climate-related projects in 2007/08. European issuers were the first to enter the nascent green bond market. In 2007, the green bond pioneer, the European Investment Bank (EIB), issued the world's first green bond, branded as a Climate Awareness Bond (CAB). [Table 1](#) lists the most important leaders among the different types of green bonds.

In practice, green and environmental, social and governance (ESG)(hence GSS+) bonds are often equated, but it is necessary to distinguish between them, which is given in [Table 2](#).

There are two basic market standards – the Green Bond Principles of the International Capital Market Association (ICMA) and the Climate Bond Standard of the Climate Bonds Initiative (CBI). The first dominates the market due to less strict requirements than the latter (EPRS, 2022). The

identification and labeling of green bonds typically follow the GBP, a set of voluntary standards established in 2014 by industry participants (including major banks such as Bank of America and BofA Securities, JP Morgan Chase & Co., Bank BNP Paribas, and HSBC Holdings plc) and non-profit organizations (Santiago, 2020). Hence, the dominant market standard is the Green Bond Principles (GBPs) (EPRS, 2022). The other most acknowledged way to identify and label a green bond is via the CBI's Climate Bonds Standard and Certification procedure. Conversely to the generality of GBP, the CBI provides some eligible criteria and a detailed green taxonomy by sector that third parties can apply to assess the qualification of a green bond (Santiago, 2020, p. 40).

Table 1: The evolution of the European green bond market

Global first	Issuer	Year
Green bond issuer	European Investment Bank*	2007
Public sector issuer	Kommunalbanken Norway	2010
Local government issuer	Île-de-France, France	2012
City issuer	City of Gothenburg, Sweden	2013
Corporate & property issuer	Vasakronan, Sweden	2013
Certified Climate Bond	Belectric Solar, UK	2014
Green covered bond	BerlinHyp, Germany	2015
Green MTN programme	Fabege, Sweden	2016
Sovereign issuer	Poland	2016

Note: *EIB is supranational and is not included in country figures.

Source: Climate Bonds Initiative (2018)

Table 2: Meaning and types of GSS+ bonds

Green bonds finance projects that have clear environmental benefits such as energy, building, or cropland efficiency.

Social bonds finance projects that create a positive social benefit such as education, housing, or health.

Sustainability bonds finance projects that combine social and environmental benefits, e.g., sustainable development goals or socially responsible investment.

Transition bonds finance projects that support the transition to net-zero. They often originate from high-polluting industries like mining, steel, and cement.

Sustainability-linked bonds (SLBs) and loans are forward-looking, performance-based instruments. The proceeds from these instruments are intended to be used for general purposes. They have coupon step-up/step-downs linked to achieving sustainability performance targets as measured against predefined key performance indicators (KPIs).

Source: Deloitte, 2023

The ICMA (2021, p. 1), within the Green Bond Principles (GBP) guidelines, describes green bonds as “any type of bond instrument where the proceeds will be exclusively applied to finance or refinance, in part or full, new and existing eligible Green Projects and aligned with the four core components of the GBP.” “The main difference between green bonds and conventional ones is that unlike the latter, the funds raised with green bonds issuance have to be entirely allocated to finance or refinance environmental-related projects, assets, or business activities that deliver environmental benefits. Like traditional fixed income securities, firms can use this debt instrument to raise capital to finance their valuable investment. With a few exceptions, green bonds are also inherently similar to conventional bonds in structure” (Santiago, 2020, p. 39). **Table 3** summarizes the various definitions of green bonds from different authors/organizations.

Following the fact that the previous definitions give a general overview of green bonds, the different types of green bonds are specified in more detail according to different observation criteria. In

the GBP, ICMA (2021) lists four types of green bonds:

- Standard green use of proceeds bonds (a standard recourse to the issuer debt obligation aligned with the GBP);
- Green revenue bond (a non-recourse-to-the-issuer debt obligation aligned with the GBP in which the credit exposure in the bond is to the pledged cash flows of the revenue streams, fees, taxes, etc., and whose use of proceeds go to related or unrelated green project(s));
- Green project bond (a project bond for a single or multiple green project(s) for which the investor has direct exposure to the risk of the project(s) with or without potential recourse to the issuer and that is aligned with the GBP), and
- Green securitized bond (collateralized by one or more specific green project/s).

Table 3: Various definitions of green bond(s)

Definition	Author(s)/organization
“A debt security issued to raise capital specifically to support climate-related environmental projects.”	World Bank, 2015, p. 9
“Green finance is finance for achieving economic growth while reducing pollution and greenhouse gas emissions, minimizing waste and improving efficiency in the use of natural resources.”	OECD, 2023, p. 14
“Green bonds are fixed fundraising funds that are reserved for fundraising specifically for climate and environmental projects for sustainability purposes.”	Niyazbekova, 2021, p.1
“Green bonds are fixed income securities issued by capital raising entities to fund their environmentally friendly projects, such as renewable energy, sustainable water management, pollution prevention, climate change adaptation and so on.”	Tang & Zang, 2020, p. 101427
„Green bonds are a financial instrument financing pro-ecological, sustainable or climate-related projects without any possible damages to the environment and the climate. In order to qualify as ‘green’, bonds must meet specific standards that are respected worldwide“.	Sobik, 2023, pp. 287-303

Source: Authors' compilation.

Relevant research papers and reports from European and global perspectives were analyzed to determine the important determinants for developing vibrant green bond markets in Europe. During the examination process, the authors used the method of observation, analysis of source material, and a method of deduction, as aligned with Frydrych (2021).

According to Banga (2018, p. 17-32), King (2017, pp. 1645-1653), and Santiago (2020, p. 47), the development of the green bond market arguably stems from the consequences of unconventional monetary policies implemented by the world's major central banks in the aftermath of the 2008 financial crisis. The failure of monetary authorities to achieve economic recovery through accommodative monetary policies has resulted in low interest rates and a hunger for yield, especially in advanced economies. Consequently, institutional investors, such as pension funds and insurance companies, are coming under pressure to find ways of making their savings products more attractive and reduce the rising costs of pension provision in the face of falling real interest rates. Such pressure has led many institutional investors to look for new investment opportunities such as green financing and

the low-carbon transition that also match their investment horizons. As one of the major market players in the fixed-income markets, institutional investors have realized that sustainable investing can preserve wealth and provide reliable revenue streams while reducing equity market volatility. This increased sustainability call and climate awareness, matched with the low-interest rate environment prevailing in most developed countries, have led institutional investors to recognize green bonds as an appealing portfolio diversification instrument.

Since the EIB issued its first green bond in 2007, the green bond market has kept expanding and becoming a well-defined area of the fixed-income markets. The evolution and growth of this market over the last few years confirm the high potential of this new financial instrument. Therefore, in the continuation of the paper, the market of green bonds was analyzed from different perspectives.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study uses descriptive statistics to analyze the green bond market. Our analysis focuses on green bonds, comparing their structures and performance in the global and European markets. Specifically, we examine the share of the global green bond market within the total Green, Social, and Sustainability (GSS+) bond market and compare the value of green bond issuances globally and within Europe. Additionally, we analyze the European green bond market by the type of issuer and the use of proceeds, and we will also focus on the emerging green bond market in Bosnia and Herzegovina (BiH). The analysis aims to identify barriers to developing the green bond market in BiH, assess the significance of market development, and propose measures to improve the market. Through this structured approach, we aim to provide a comprehensive understanding of the green bond market's dynamics and the challenges faced in developing regions. Furthermore, we will employ methods of analysis and deduction to conclude the collected data, ensuring a thorough examination of the market trends and challenges.

Cumulative data for the European and global green bond market from 2013 to 2023 were used to analyze the green bond market. The amounts for Bosnia and Herzegovina will be measured in BAM, while the data for the European area will be measured in USD, referring to Climate Bonds Initiative (2018). The data were collected from the following sources: Climate Bonds Initiative (CBI), Institute for Energy Economics and Financial Analysis (IEEFA), Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), Bloomberg, S&P Global Ratings, and Banja Luka Stock Exchange (BLSE). Secondary data will be collected from these sources to conduct the analysis.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The global market for sustainability-related use-of-proceeds bonds, including green, social, and sustainability bonds, has seen remarkable growth in recent years. Green bonds, in particular, have dominated this market, driven by the urgent need to address climate issues. This chapter analyzes the share of green bonds within the total GSS+ market, exploring the trends and underlying factors contributing to their prominence.

4.1. Global and European green bonds market analysis

4.1.1. Analysis of the share of the global green bond market in the total GSS+ market

Issuance of green and other types of sustainability-related use-of-proceeds bonds has surged in the past few years. A recent CBI analysis found that most of the volume has been from green bonds. However, social and sustainability bonds have also seen notable increases in recent years (Deloitte,

2023, p. 7) (see *Table 4*).

Table 4: Green and other types of sustainability-related bond global issuance volume, 2019-2023 (in billion USD)

Bill. USD	Green bond	Social bond	Sustainability bond	Sustainability-linked bond	Transition bond	Total
2019	265	19	53	4	1	342
2020	308	170	137	9	3	627
2021	570	221	200	97	4	1092
2022	523	175	151	77	4	930
2023	575	181	159	66	3	984

Source: S&P Global Ratings, 2024, p. 8

The prevalence of green bonds may be linked to the market's perceived climate issues as more urgent than social ones, as represented by many international initiatives such as the Glasgow Financial Alliance for Net Zero or the Paris Agreement. Moreover, climate-related action can be more easily priced if compared to social issues since, in the climate-related action field, there are straightforward metrics and impact indicators, such as reduction of greenhouse gas emissions and reduction of the risk of adverse impact of current climate conditions on economic activities (OECD, 2023).

4.1.2. Comparison of global and European green bond markets by issue value

Green bond issuance globally and in Europe has experienced a tumultuous couple of years after reaching record highs of USD 575 billion and USD 326 billion in 2021, respectively. Global issuances dropped 8% in 2022 amid tightened macroeconomic conditions, while Europe saw a milder decrease at 6%. In 2023, Europe's green bond issuance recovered 11% year on year to USD 341 billion. It slightly outperformed the global markets, which recorded 10% growth to reach USD 581 billion. Both surpassed 2021 levels, as illustrated in *Figure 1*.

Figure 1: Europe green bond issuance vs. global green bond issuance (in billion USD)

Source: IEEFA, 2024, p. 7

Europe remains the largest issuance region, accounting for more than half of global issuance, and is the focus of this paper. Europe's recent outperformance compared to other regions has reinforced

its position as a continued driving force in the global market.

4.1.3. Analysis of the European green bond market by type of issuers

Long-term structural green bond growth will likely be driven by all broad issuer types, as achieving climate goals requires all market participants to act. Given the size of the climate funding gap, a sustainable share of the investment must come from private finance. However, the role of public finance will remain vital as a catalyst. This is illustrated in **Figure 2**, where the dominance of the public sector in the issuance of green bonds in Europe can be seen in 2023.

Figure 2: European green bond issuance by type of issuers in 2023

Source: IEEFA, 2024, p. 8.

Figure 3: MDBs GSS bonds issuance, 2007-2022 (in billion USD)

Source: OECD, 2023, p. 14.

According to the OECD report (2023, p.14), in the green bonds market, MDBs were the sole issuers until 2012. From a conceptual point of view, MDBs have played a multifaceted role in the green, social, and sustainability bond market. GSS bond issuance by MDBs has grown consistently over

the years, while market shares have greatly varied mainly because of the different types of issuers entering the market. MDBs now comprise a small share of the green bonds market, dominated by corporates. At the same time, they still make up a significant fraction of recent social and sustainability bonds issuances, as these two market segments are still in an early stage of development. Volumes confirm the substantial role of MDBs in GSS markets. *Figure 3* shows self-reported GSS bond issuance of multilateral development banks in 2022 adjusted USD billions (OECD, 2023).

As *Figure 3* shows, green bonds were issued more frequently by MDBs than their social counterparts. The main reasons can be attributed to the more extended existence of the green bond market than social bonds. General and MDBs' social bond issuance increased rapidly during the COVID-19 pandemic because of emergency needs for economic support in distressed times. It is now consolidating its presence in GSS bond issuer's balance sheets regardless of Covid-19 (OECD, 2023). MDBs can pool capital to green projects and provide credibility and anchor support to other green or sustainable bond issuers, especially in emerging markets and developing economies.

Indeed, a market pioneered by large development banks came from issuers different than multilateral development banks. Consequently, an even broader group of investors started being attracted by green bonds, such as asset managers, pension funds, companies, foundations, and religious organizations (IEEFA, 2024). Between 2010 and 2014, USD 57.9 billion in labeled green bonds were issued globally, with USD 36.6 billion just in 2014. It was the first year with prominent corporate participation, representing 33% of 2014's total issuance. From 2014 onwards, the green bond market experienced significant growth, as Santiago (2020) noted. This can be seen in *Figure 4*, where the volume of emissions by type of issuers in Europe is shown.

Figure 4: The volume of green bond issuance in Europe by type of issuers (in billion USD)

Source: Climate Bonds Initiative (<https://www.climatebonds.net/market/data/>, Accessed: May 25, 2024)

Consistent with trends observed in 2022, the corporate sector drove the green volume in 2023, contributing to 57% of the total issuance. Non-financial corporate issuers contributed 29% of the 2023 market share spread over 692 aligned green instruments, amassing USD 171.8 billion. Financial

corporates emerged as the second-largest issuer type with a 28% share of aligned green volumes. Sovereigns will likely continue issuing green bonds to fund their intervention and incentive subsidies, research and development support, public infrastructure and building decarbonization, and other expenditures to achieve their Nationally Determined Contributions. For example, the governments of France, Germany, the UK, and Italy were among the top 10 global green bond issuers in 2023, and are among the top 10 globally of all time.

Corporate issues in Europe are dominated mainly by the energy, utilities, automotive, transport, and building sectors, which have been dependent on fossil fuels. Despite still navigating the current high-interest rate environment, corporate issuers will continue to require financing to support their environmental strategies and energy transition plans. Financial institutions, especially banks, act as both issuers and arrangers of green bonds. They are expanding their green financing capabilities to channel private capital toward net-zero goals, partly supported by issuing green bonds themselves. Increasing pressure on financial institutions to decarbonize their facilitated emissions – beyond financed emissions – will also incentivize them to increase their green capital market underwriting capabilities and advisory services to help corporate issuers implement green financing strategies (IEEFA, 2024). This will support the overall growth of the green bond market.

4.1.4. Analysis of the European green bond market according to use of proceeds

Investment in low-carbon buildings and energy efficiency projects continued to be the most common green projects financed by the utilization of the bond proceeds. However, this sector declined in 2022 compared to 2021, followed by growth in 2023. Investment in the transport sector was the second most important item after investment in buildings and energy efficiency, and among the less important were water, waste, land use, industry, ICT, and unspecified A&R (see *Figure 5*).

Figure 5: Use of proceeds (in billion USD)

Source: Climate Bonds Initiative (<https://www.climatebonds.net/market/data/>, Accessed: May 25, 2024)

4.2. Green bond market in BiH

The green bond market in BiH can be said to be emerging. It started in 2023, when the first issue of green bonds was announced on the local capital market. Viewed from the perspective of previous

analyses, the issue of green bonds on the BiH capital market represents an issue by a private institution from the financial sector and specifically has the characteristic of “ESG bonds.” Therefore, green bonds issued by financial institutions are the only type of green bonds on the BiH capital market.

The first financial institution in the Western Balkans region that announced a public call for registration and payment of the first issue of green (more precisely, ESG) bonds on the local (Banja Luka) stock exchange is Naša Banka ad Banja Luka in October 2023. The expected effects were the strengthening and dispersion of the credit portfolio, as well as the strengthening of the bank’s position in the financial services market in general, as well as meeting the needs of clients in the BiH market, as well as the application of ESG principles in the bank’s operations. Naša banka and Banja Luka realized two issues of green bonds; the issues’ terms are listed in the following two tables, *Table 5* and *Table 6*.

Table 5: Conditions for the first issue of green (ESG) bonds of Naša banka ad Banja Luka

Characteristic	Explanation
Number of issued bonds	70,000
Individual face value	100.00 BAM
Total face value	7,000,000.00 BAM
Issue currency	BAM
It will be due	7 (seven) years
Method of payment of principal and interest	In the first two years, only interest will be paid semi-annually (grace period). After that, the principal and interest will be paid in equal semi-annual annuities for the remaining five years.
The amount of the interest rate	5.15%
Deadline for payment of principal and interest	Suppose the Validator, after the performed validation, determines that the Issuer has met the objectives stipulated in the Decision on the first issue of ESG bonds through a public offer. In that case, the interest rate will not change until the maturity of the first issue of ESG bonds, i.e., it will be 5.15% on an annual basis. Suppose the Validator, after the performed validation, determines that the Issuer has not met the goals stipulated in the Decision on the first issue of ESG bonds through a public offering. In that case, the interest rate is increased by 0.20 percentage points, that is, from the next annuity (from the eighth annuity) it will be 5.35% until the maturity of the first issue of ESG bonds.

Source: https://cms.blberza.com/api/files/cms2/docver/107983/files/NA%c5%a0A%20BANKA_Jedinstveni%20prospekt%20prve%20emisije%20ESG%20obveznica_f.pdf, Accessed: May 18, 2024

The issuer will place the funds collected through this bond issue for the approval of loans for products related to sustainable development, i.e., as a priority with the reduction of CO2 emissions, and, in connection with this, two credit products are planned that will be financed with the funds collected through this issue:

- Long-term loan for financing products that result in the reduction of CO2 emissions for individuals and
- Long-term loan for financing products that result in the reduction of CO2 emissions for legal entities.

The purpose of these loans is, among other things, related to the purchase of heat pumps, solar

panels, and electric cars, as well as all other purposes that lead to the reduction of CO₂ emissions, with the possibility of refinancing invoices for fixed assets and equipment paid for a maximum of 12 months from the date of credit application. The expected effects are the strengthening and dispersion of the credit portfolio, as well as the strengthening of the bank's capital position to realize the projected growth of the bank, the strengthening of the issuer's position on the market of financial services in general, meeting the needs of clients processed by the issuer on the market of BiH, as well as involvement in the application of ESG principles into the issuer's operations.

Table 6: Conditions for the second issue of green (ESG) bonds by Naša Banka ad Banja Luka

Characteristic	Explanation
Number of issued bonds	42,000
Individual face value	100.00 BAM
Total face value	4,200,000.00 BAM
Issue currency	BAM
It will be due	7 (seven) years
Method of payment of principal and interest	In the initial period of the first five years, only interest will be paid semi-annually (grace period). After that, the principal and interest will be paid in equal semiannual annuities for the remaining two years.
The amount of the interest rate	5.25%
Deadline for payment of principal and interest	Suppose the Validator, after the validation, determines that the Issuer has met the CO ₂ reduction goal stipulated in the Decision on the second issue of ESG bonds. In that case, the interest rate will not change until the maturity of the second issue of ESG bonds, i.e., it will be 5.25% annually. Suppose the Validator, after the validation, determines that the Issuer has not met the CO ₂ reduction goal stipulated in the Decision on the second issue of ESG bonds. In that case, the interest rate is increased by 0.20 percentage points, i.e., from the next annuity (from the eighth annuity), it will be 5.45 % until the maturity of the second issue of ESG bonds.

Source: <https://cms.blberza.com/api/files/cms2/docver/108596/files/Jedinstveni%20prospekt%20druge%20emisije%20obveznica.pdf>, Accessed: May 18, 2024

By raising funds through the issuance of ESG bonds, the issuer wishes to perform optimal liquidity management by providing stable and long-term sources of financing in local currency, as well as to ensure further diversification of sources of funds for its business, while also wishing to make its contribution to the development of the capital market in BiH entity of Republic of Srpska and to contribute to the reduction of CO₂ emissions. Therefore, the issuance of green bonds will represent sources of financing for other market participants. Moreover, credit institutions' issuance of green bonds encourages the development of green financing practices and other green financial instruments. This is where the role of banks as critical suppliers of capital changes under the conditions of a bank-centric financial system, like the one present in BiH (Ibrić, 2024). It is precisely this bank-centricity that shows us that bank products, in the form of loans, are the most common source of financing for the economy, i.e., corporate sector, while issues of corporate bonds in BiH are very little represented on the capital market.¹

4.3. Barriers to the green bonds market development – the case of BiH

Obstacles to the development of the green bond market, problems for issuers and investors, and

¹ <https://www.ekapija.com/en/news/4658799/green-bonds-have-arrived-on-the-bih-market-what-are-they-for>,

issues in the external review market exist. According to Sobik (2023), barriers to the development of the green bond market can be divided into two groups: institutional barriers (institutional barriers) and market barriers, as shown in *Table 7*.

Table 7: Primary barriers to the green bonds market development

Institutional barriers	Market barriers
The lack of a unified standard for issuing green bonds	The small size of emissions
A uniform standard for reporting to investors	Currency risk
Legal risk	High transaction costs
Regulatory uncertainty and political instability regarding energy and climate policy	

Source: Banga (2018, p. 20) & Sobik (2023, p. 297)

In addition to the barriers to the development of the green bond market (barriers to the green bond market development), the European Commission states that a barrier is related to a lack of investable projects and assets. Furthermore, it is considered that these barriers can lead to consequences such as (EPRS, 2022):

- Potential future market disruption from greenwashing,
- Not enough high-quality green bonds being issued compared to market demand,
- There is a risk that not enough investment will be channelled toward projects with a substantial impact.

Considering the expected growth of the green bond market, these vulnerabilities are also likely to grow. They may increase the risk of high-impact/visible greenwashing incidents creating severe reputational problems. The bond market in Bosnia and Herzegovina is still relatively small compared to Western Europe. Nevertheless, there is space for development following the development of the BiH financial market and economy in the coming years. The lack of appropriate institutional arrangements for green bond management, the issue of minimum size, and high transaction costs associated with issuing green bonds are the key barriers to the development of green bonds in developing countries.

4.4. The importance of the development of the green bond market

Some authors (e.g., Tang & Zhang, 2018; Santiago, 2020) argue that from the issuers' perspective, green bonds can expand the breadth of ownership, enlarge their investor base, and potentially obtain a lower cost of capital and longer tenor compared with straight conventional bonds. For investors, green bonds may satisfy their green mandate and boost their ESG score. The green label makes it simple for institutional investors, who have increasingly made climate change commitments, to identify green investment. Bonds are also appropriate vehicles to tap into their extensive capital holdings at scale. For example, green bonds, primarily to finance infrastructure, can offer long-term maturities, being a good fit with institutional investors' long-term liabilities and allowing asset-liability matching.

5. CONCLUDING REMARKS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study analyzes the European green bond market from various perspectives. Issuance of green and other types of sustainability-related use-of-proceeds bonds has surged in the past few years. A

recent CBI analysis has found that most of the volume comes from green bonds, although social and sustainability bonds have also noted increases in recent years.

Europe remains the largest issuance region, accounting for over half of global issuance. Green bond issuance globally and in Europe has experienced a tumultuous couple of years after reaching record highs of USD 575 billion and USD 326 billion in 2021, respectively. Global issuances dropped 8% in 2022 amid tightened macroeconomic conditions, while Europe registered a milder decrease at 6%. In 2023, Europe's green bond issuance recovered 11% year on year to USD 341 billion. It slightly outperformed the global markets, which recorded 10% growth to reach USD 581 billion. Long-term structural green bond growth will likely be driven by all broad issuer types, as achieving climate goals requires all market participants to act. Consistent with trends observed in 2022, the corporate sector drove the green volume in 2023, contributing to 57% of the total issuance. Non-financial corporate issuers contributed 29% of the 2023 market share spread over 692. Financial corporates emerged as the second-largest issuer type with a 28% share of aligned green volumes. Sovereigns will likely continue issuing green bonds to fund their intervention and incentive subsidies, research and development support, public infrastructure and building decarbonization, and other expenditures to achieve their nationally determined contributions. Corporate issuers in Europe are dominated mainly by the energy, utilities, automotive, transport, and building sectors, all of which have historically been dependent on fossil fuels.

Analysis of the capital markets in BiH indicates that the green bond market is emerging, and it started in 2023, when the first issue of green bonds was announced on the local capital market (i.e., Banja Luka Stock Exchange). Given that a commercial bank participated in both issues of green bonds, green bonds issued by a financial institution are the only type of green bond on BiH's capital markets. The value of issues on the green bond market in BiH was BAM 11.2 million.

The lack of appropriate institutional arrangements for green bond management, the issue of minimum size, and the high transaction costs associated with issuing green bonds are the key barriers to developing green bonds in developing countries. To cope with these challenges, referring to research findings from Bang (2018, pp. 30-32), we suggest the use of multilateral and national development banks as intermediary institutions for managing local green bonds. Furthermore, local governments are required to provide local green bond issuers with guarantees aimed at covering the transaction costs associated with green bond issuance.

Declarations

The authors have no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose. The data are available upon a reasonable request from the corresponding author.

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Are Islamic bonds a safe choice for portfolio diversification in time of crisis? Evidence from volatility-causality analysis of Dubai financial market Here

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ABSTRACT

Despite the popularity and uniqueness of Sukuk as an alternative tradable financing tool, the effectiveness of these products in portfolio allocation and diversification still needs to be improved. This paper employs the multivariate BEKK-GARCH (1,1) model to analyze shocks and volatility based on the daily prices of the Dubai Islamic Capital Market (Sukuk Index) and the conventional stock market (DFM Index). Additionally, it applies Johansen co-integration and Granger causality to investigate the persistence of shocks and volatility in long-term relationships and the leading relationship between Islamic and conventional markets. The results validate the impact of their respective news feeds on both Sukuk and stock market indices and demonstrate the persistence of volatility throughout the studied period from April 2009 to December 2020. The causality test reveals a multidirectional relationship between Sukuk and stocks, each contributing to the other's growth. The study confirms that Sukuk is not a safe haven for portfolio diversification in the Dubai financial market.

ARTICLE HISTORY

Received: June 19, 2024

Accepted: June 20, 2024

Published: June 30, 2024

KEYWORDS

volatility; sukuk; stock market; financial crisis; Bekk-garch; Granger causality

JEL CODES

D12; E21; N35;

HOW TO CITE

Metadjer, W., Avdukic, A., & Camdzic, E. (2024). Are Islamic bonds a safe choice for portfolio diversification in time of crisis? Evidence from volatility-causality analysis of Dubai financial market Here. *Journal of Economics, Law and Society*, 1(1), 73-89. <https://doi.org/10.70009/jels.2024.1.1.5>

1. INTRODUCTION

Considering the global development of the Muslim community and their continuing need for a fully coherent and integrated financial and economic framework that adheres to their beliefs and religion, the world witnessed the incredible growth of the Islamic finance and halal industry in both Muslim and non-Muslim countries (Mustafa et al., 2018). This has led to a growing focus on Islamic finance as an ethical and sustainable financial system guided by a set of rules derived from traditional Islamic sources. The global Sukuk market is one area of Islamic finance that has attracted and continues to attract much interest from the global business community (Seda et al., 2020). *Sukuk* is the plural of *Sakk*, an Arabic term that means certificate; in a financial sense, it refers to a Shari'ah-compliant bond (AAOIFI, 2008).

The global economic uncertainty and subsequent crisis exposed the vulnerability of conventional financial markets (Aracil, 2019); the previous financial and current pandemic crises illuminated the interconnectedness between international and regional markets (Akhtaruzzaman et al., 2020). The recent COVID-19 pandemic has jeopardized the economic growth of both developed and developing countries. In addition to the stimulus programs to counteract the economic shock caused by

the pandemic, policymakers are looking for new ways to rebuild the economy (Hasan et al., 2022). Nevertheless, Islamic financial markets have shown extraordinary performance and sustainable growth during the financial crisis compared to their conventional counterparts (Arif et al., 2021). Given the global expansion of Islamic financial markets and the proven connectedness of international markets (Samitas et al., 2021), it is no surprise that investigating further the nature of the correlation and volatility persistence between these two markets became a must for both economists and investors (Paltrinieri et al., 2018).

Investors, policymakers, and other finance practitioners around the world have become increasingly interested in forecasting financial market correlations and volatility persistence because of the importance of a good modeling process and meticulously drawn guidance for portfolio allocation (Poon & Granger, 2003). As a result, researchers are decorating both conventional and Islamic markets to gain a deeper understanding of their functioning dynamics (Nazlioglu et al., 2015).

Researchers and econometricians find it challenging to study the volatility of a specific asset or market due to its time-varying nature and dependence on market evolution and time series (Engle, 1993). There is considerable literature that examines the relation, similarities, and impact of sukuk and bonds, as well as Islamic stocks and conventional stocks; however, studies about sukuk as Islamic alternative fixed-income securities and conventional stocks still need to be made available.

Therefore, this paper investigates the nature of the interrelationship between Sukuk and stocks, which may have significant implications for the portfolio allocation strategy. It also examines the safe-haven likelihood of Sukuk relative to stocks and the causality directions between both markets. This paper aims to provide significant recommendations to international investors by analyzing the shocks and volatility persistence of both the Islamic and conventional financial markets. Additionally, it seeks to shed light on the nature of this relationship by examining the causality between both markets and addressing the questions of who is driving whom (Haque et al., 2018).

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 reviews the existing literature from theoretical and empirical perspectives. Section 3 details the specific methodology used in this study and the findings of the modeling processes. The results and implications are presented in Section 4, while Section 5 offers concluding remarks.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

According to the principles of Shari'ah and *Usul al-Fiqh* (Islamic jurisprudence), a well-integrated and developed Islamic financial system still exposes Islamic financial markets to potential risks (Iqbal, 2007). Scholars and researchers in the field of Islamic finance have extensively explored associated risk types (Shahari & Saifur, 2021; Belkhaoui et al., 2020; El-Massah et al., 2019), as well as risk management in Islamic finance (Elgharbawy, 2020; Asma et al., 2018; Ahmed, 2011). Elgari (2003) defined risk in Arabic as 'Mukhatarah, characterizing it as a situation where deviation from the plan could lead to an unusual or uncommon outcome. "Mukhatarah" and "gharar" (deception) are often associated with danger or risk. However, *gharar* can also indicate a circumstance in which one party to a contract has information about some aspects of the contract that the other party does not have or in which neither party has control over the subject of the contract. Thus, Elgari (2003) views the prohibition of *gharar* as a risk-mitigation strategy that prevents transactions with high information content inequality. However, the Islamic paradigm does not forbid achieving gains or engaging in financial transactions to establish a prosperous and prosperous industry or company. However, the principle of *al-kharaj bil dhaman* (profit follows responsibility) in Islam, as stated by Qahf and Khan in 1992, dictates that any generated revenue must come with a corresponding obligation to cover potential losses.

2.1. Sukuk and risk management

Financial markets, portfolio management, and investments, both in conventional and Islamic financial markets, are closely associated with the term ‘uncertainty.’ Indeed, ‘doubt’ is a powerful emotion, particularly in the finance sector, where investors worldwide strive to reduce this feeling, particularly about their portfolio and investment allocation (Fisher & Statman, 2000). Consequently, doubt and uncertainty arise when deciding which security to include in a portfolio that could potentially incur significant costs. Therefore, risk managers aim to reduce uncertainty or risk exposure while maximizing potential gains from a particular transaction, investment, or allocation.

Sukuk has garnered significant attention in the risk management literature, prompting further research and studies on this particularly significant topic (Muhamed et al., 2022; Saheed & Sikiru, 2022; Balli et al., 2021). Indeed, faith-ethical-based investors constantly seek a safe haven for their portfolio allocation compliant with their religious and/or moral orientation (Naeem et al., 2021; Bugar et al., 2022). However, the study by Lai et al. (2019) finds that sukuk are only a partial safe haven in the extreme market. In this case, sukuk are not an exception, and the appetite for these alternative financial tools shows an increased tendency amid the economic uncertainty; indeed, numbers point out the continuously growing issuing of sukuk during the COVID-19 pandemic (Keshminder et al., 2022). According to global data provider Refinitiv, sukuk issuances internationally set a record in 2020, reaching a total of \$172.1 billion, compared to \$169.1 billion in 2019 (Refinitiv, 2020).

Sukuk investors possess undivided beneficial ownership of the underlying assets, which entitles the certificate holders to shares of revenues generated from them (Afshar, 2013). Conventional bonds, on the other hand, signify a contractual debt obligation that requires the issuer to pay interest to the debt holder on a designated date (Thomas et al., 2005). Investors place a high value on price changes and volatility movements of various securities and asset classes to create the most viable group of assets that offer the best possible returns versus the least possible risks (Jondeau & Rockinger, 2006). Therefore, in financial markets, it is important to analyze, assess, study, and research all relevant information for investment and decision-making (Virlics, 2013).

Because markets are connected and depend on each other, there is a chance that volatility will spread from major international markets to regional ones (Islam & Volkov, 2021; Gallo and Velluchi, 2009). This is more likely because information can instantly reach markets (Erdogan et al., 2020). Volatility spillover may occur among different topographical locations as well as between different categories of financial markets (Ng, 2000), such as between the bond markets (Abakah et al., 2021), the oil markets (Ahmed et al., 2022), and the Islamic stock markets (Ben Rejeb, 2017).

Previously, Connolly et al. (2005) analyzed the relationship between Islamic and conventional markets. According to their research, the stock-bonds connection decreases as stock market uncertainty increases, implying that bonds may be a superior hedge against stock market downturns. El Khalichi et al. (2014) used variance ratio tests to compare the random walk hypothesis to see how well Islamic indices and their traditional counterparts worked. Their findings reveal that Islamic indices have the same efficiency as conventional indices. El Alaoui et al. (2015) also used wavelet analysis to examine how the returns on the Islamic Dubai Financial Market (DFM-UAE) index changed over time and how they are related to the returns on other regional Islamic indices. The findings reveal that nearby markets tend to have a contagion effect, exhibiting increased correlation and interdependence with a specific time delay.

Furthermore, many other researchers (Naifar, 2015; Sclip et al., 2016) investigated the topic from the volatility perspective. In the context of Saudi Arabia, for instance, Naifar (2015) investigated the structural relationship between Islamic bond yields, stock market returns, and volatility in Saudi Arabia. Gumbel, Clayton, and Frank are three Archimedean copula models used by the author. The

study's findings reveal that the dependency structure between sukuk yields and stock market volatility is symmetric and has the same amplitude. Using the same approach, Sclip et al. (2016) demonstrated that volatility connections between sukuk and regional market indices are stronger during financial crashes. According to the researchers, sukuk have lower volatility than equities, so they could be a valuable and viable diversifier for the investor's portfolio.

Seth and Singhania (2019) analyze frontier markets' cointegration using BEKK and DCC GARCH models. They argue that there needs to be cointegration between the markets in the long run, which opens the door to non-negligible investment opportunities. Thus, long-term investors could make some profits by adding the financial assets from the non-cointegrated frontier markets to their portfolios; however, investors still have to be careful when forming their portfolios and investment strategies; they have to think smart and reflect on the implementation of diversified assets as well as employ adequate risk management strategies during the period of financial crisis in order to protect themselves against any possible financial losses (Rana & Akhter, 2015).

This paper contributes to the literature on comparative analysis of sukuk and conventional bonds by elaborating on the risk elements and challenges of sukuk and bonds in the light of risk management. Considering the extensive literature available, this paper provides insight into the riskiness of sukuk for potential investors as an alternative financial tool.

3. METHODOLOGICAL PROCESS AND FINDINGS

It is critical to analyze and forecast the volatility of securities, assets, indices, or markets before investing. Financial market volatility is the intensity of price changes in financial instruments; the more volatile the assets, the riskier they are on the market (Shiller, 1992). Typically, we evaluate the forecast performance of volatility models using statistical efficiency criteria like mean squared error or net value, considering specific economic applications like value-at-risk or portfolio allocation (Clements & Silvennoinen, 2009). Poon and Granger (2003, 2005) present a comprehensive statistical assessment of forecast performance, whereas Andersen et al. (2006) explore a variety of volatility models based on economic settings. The most straightforward approach to understanding the correlation is to consider it a link between two assets; we refer to the correlation using a coefficient between 1 and -1. In the financial market, a positive correlation coefficient indicates that two assets will move together. A negative coefficient of correlation implies a negative relationship between the two assets, resulting in a rise in one asset price and a fall in the other.

The conditional volatility model is undeniably the best and most commonly used model for time-varying and volatility analysis for high-frequency data extracted daily or even hourly. The literature widely recognizes the fundamental stochastic framework that directly relates to the conditions and regularity stipulations of one of the most famous univariate conditional volatility models, such as GARCH (Nugroho et al., 2019; Zeitlberger & Brauneis, 2016).

However, even if the use of multidimensional or multivariate GARCH (MGARCH) models in financial market studies has been widespread, the latter needs to be better established than the univariate GARCH model. We can mention Bollerslev's early work (1990) on the changing variance structure of the exchange rate regime in the European Monetary System, assuming the correlations to be time-invariant. Lien and Luo (1994) evaluated the multi-period hedge ratios of currency futures in an MGARCH framework. Karolyi (1995) examined the international transmission of stock returns and volatility using different versions of MGARCH models for short-run return and volatility dynamics.

This study employs the bivariate BEKK-GARCH (1,1) model to examine shocks and volatility based on the daily prices of Dubai Islamic Capital Market (Sukuk Index) and conventional stock market (DFM index) prices, extracted from the Thomson Reuters database and investing database,

respectively, from April 1, 2009, to December 29, 2020.

Oil and energy market analysis more widely employs parametric approaches, which provide non-trivial functions of historical values and observable variables. We investigate the most popular methods using the generalized autoregressive conditional heteroskedasticity (GARCH) model to produce volatility estimates at different time scales. Unlike non-parametric techniques, these conditional models fit data using maximum likelihood estimation and may account for exogenous factors (Matar et al., 2013).

Extending our Univariate-GARCH(1.1) allows to estimate the variance-covariance matrix. We specify the mean equation of the SUKUK and stock market return series as follows:

$$P_{su} = \gamma_{su} + \vartheta_{su}P_{su_{t-1}} + \varepsilon_{su} \tag{Eq. 4}$$

$$P_{st} = \gamma_{st} + \vartheta_{st}P_{st_{t-1}} + \varepsilon_{st} \tag{Eq. 5}$$

where P_{su}, P_{st} : are vectors of definite return of sukuk and stock market series, respectively; $\vartheta_{su}, \vartheta_{st}$: are the autoregressive coefficient in the conditional mean equation for sukuk and stock market returns; γ_{su}, γ_{st} : are the long drift coefficient. $\varepsilon_{su}, \varepsilon_{st}$: are the residuals.

Baba-Engle-Kraft-Kroner (BEKK) model refers to the specific parameterization of the multivariate GARCH model developed by Engle and Kroner (1995). The most straightforward Bekk representation for the $N \times N$ conditional covariance matrix Ω takes the form:

$$\Omega_t = c'c + \sum_{K=1}^K B'\Omega_{t-1}B + \sum_{k=1}^k A'\varepsilon_{t-1}\varepsilon'_{t-1} - 1 \tag{Eq. 6}$$

where C is an upper triangular $N \times N$ matrix, A and B are unrestricted $N \times N$ matrices and quadratic representation automatically guarantees that Ω is positive definite.

We can show our diagonal BEKK-GARCH(1.1), $N=2$ as follow:

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{pmatrix} \Omega_{su,t} & \Omega_{su\ st,t} \\ \Omega_{st\ su,t} & \Omega_{st,t} \end{pmatrix} &= \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_{su,t} & 0 \\ \alpha_{st\ su,t} & \alpha_{st,t} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_{su,t} & \alpha_{su\ st,t} \\ \alpha_{st\ su,t} & 0 \end{pmatrix} \\ &+ \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{su,t} & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_{st,t} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \Omega_{su,t-1} & \Omega_{su\ st,t-1} \\ \Omega_{st\ su,t-1} & \Omega_{st,t-1} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{su,t} & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_{st,t} \end{pmatrix} \\ &+ \begin{pmatrix} \beta_{su,t} & 0 \\ 0 & \beta_{st,t} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_{su,t-1}^2 & \varepsilon_{su,t-1}\varepsilon_{st,t-1} \\ \varepsilon_{st,t-1}\varepsilon_{su,t-1} & \varepsilon_{st,t-1}^2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \beta_{su,t} & 0 \\ 0 & \beta_{st,t} \end{pmatrix} \end{aligned} \tag{Eq. 7}$$

Hence, the diagonal BEKK-GARCH (1.1) is:

$$\Omega_{su,t} = \alpha_{su}^2 + \sigma_{su}^2\Omega_{su,t-1} + \beta_{su}^2\varepsilon_{su,t-1}^2 \tag{Eq. 8}$$

$$\Omega_{su,t} = \alpha_{su}\alpha_{st} + \sigma_{su}\Omega_{su,t-1} + \beta_{su}\beta_{st}\varepsilon_{su,t-1}\varepsilon_{st,t-1} \tag{Eq. 9}$$

$$\Omega_{st,t} = \left\{ (\alpha_{st,su}^2 + \alpha_{st}^2) + \sigma_{st}^2\Omega_{st,t-1} + \beta_{st}^2\varepsilon_{st,t-1}^2 \right\} \tag{Eq. 10}$$

In addition to the multivariate GARCH model, we have run the Johansen cointegration test, the Granger causality test, and the Impulse response Function to investigate any long-run relationship between our variables and to shed light on the nature of this relationship.

For that reason, we had to select the adequate lag length criterion. A Vector Auto Regressive model VAR has to be specified. Our bivariate VAR model is represented as follows:

$$ST_t = \sum_{I=1}^P \alpha_{1i} ST_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^p \beta_{1i} SU_{t-1} + \varepsilon_{t1} \quad (\text{Eq. 11})$$

$$SU_t = \sum_{I=1}^P \alpha_{2i} SU_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^p \beta_{2i} ST_{t-1} + \varepsilon_{t2} \quad (\text{Eq. 12})$$

Johansen's cointegration test allows us to determine the long-run cointegration between the time series used in our study.

Two tests in the Johansen method exist, though, in our paper, we rely on the Trace statistic (λ trace) for each rank r .

Our model has two endogenous variables, r being 0 or 1. In this case, the null hypothesis is that the rank is at most r versus the alternative hypothesis, which is that the rank is firmly larger than this r (Johansen, 1992).

Which implies that $H_0: r=0$ against $H_1: r>0$, if the (λ trace) is higher than the critical value of the Johansen-Juselius, we reject H_0 and accept H_1 , that there exists a long-run relationship between our variables.

Granger Causality test and Impulse response functions will be used to examine the inter-relationship between Islamic and Conventional markets and whether Sukuk and Stocks are useful for studying, predicting, and forecasting each other.

We consider the following assumptions for Granger test:

$$H5. \quad ST = f(SU)$$

$$H6. \quad SU = f(ST)$$

The **Figure 1** below shows the prices of stocks and sukuk, respectively, for the selected period, and it is clear that both time series are evolving. From 2012 to 2014, both sukuk and stocks experienced a significant price increase, with sukuk reaching nearly 250 points and stocks reaching nearly 190.

The graphs indicate a slight decrease in prices from mid-2015 to the beginning of 2019, with sukuk prices remaining between 150 and 160 points and stock prices fluctuating between 120 and 150 points, indicating that stock prices are more volatile than sukuk. In 2019, we observed a significant decline in both sukuk and stock prices, reaching a low of 100 points before they rose again.

According to global data source Refinitiv, total sukuk issuances worldwide established a new record in 2020, reaching \$172.1 billion, up from \$169.1 billion in 2019.

Sukuk issuances improved significantly during the first nine months of 2020, as COVID-19 lockdown actions and a drop in oil prices encouraged a flow in sovereign issuance in key sukuk markets. This is intended to fund large-scale incentive plans to modify the epidemic's economic impacts.

Figure 6: Stock, sukuk prices and returns

Source: Authors's own.

3.1. Reliability tests

In general, time series have a unit root, which refers to a random walk with drift. To check the stationarity of our variables, we use two of the most popular unit root tests, as shown in [Table 1](#).

Table 8: Unit root test statistics

Variables	Philips Peron test with constant and trend (1%)			Augmented Dickey Fuller test with constant and trend (1%)		
	level	1 st dif	result	level	1 st dif	result
R_su	0.0000	0.0000	I(0)	0.0000	0.0001	I(0)
R_st	0.0000	0.0000	I(0)	0.0000	0.0000	I(0)

Source: Authors's own.

The results of both PP and ADF tests show that the variables are stationary at level and do not have unit root because their probability is lower than the critical value.

The co-integration (trace test) results shown in [Table 3](#) imply that there is a co-integrating equation at the 0.05 level. Hence, there is a long-run equilibrium relationship between the Sukuk and the stock market in the Dubai financial market.

3.2. Empirical results for BEKK

[Table 2](#) represents Fascia 1 and 2, which show the conditional mean and variance-covariance results, respectively. First, panel 1 illustrates that one period-lagged sukuk price ϑ_{su} describes the changes in the current sukuk price Y_{su} , the same for the stock market index. This means that historical prices are denoted by actual prices, which are in accordance with an efficient market hypothesis (Timmermann & Granger, 2004).

Table 9: BEKK GARCH estimation mode

Variables	Coefficients	Std. error	z-stat	p-value
<i>panel 1</i>				
γ_{su}	0.044149	0.083780	0.526959	0.0000
O_{su}	0.167594	0.057975	2.890783	0.0000
γ_{st}	0.038879	0.082842	0.469322	0.0000
O_{st}	0.201221	0.055467	3.627757	0.0000
<i>panel 2</i>				
α_{su}	1.261919	0.072957	17.29674	0.0000
$\alpha_{su,st}$	1.705330	0.074915	22.76340	0.0000
α_{st}	2.150441	0.088538	24.28821	0.0000
β_{su}	-0.372512	0.014059	-26.49601	0.0000
β_{st}	-0.390124	0.017449	-22.35771	0.0000
σ_{su}	0.832046	0.010755	77.36389	0.0000
σ_{st}	0.655270	0.018029	36.34463	0.0000

Source: Authors' own.

Second, the panel 2 part of the table shows that ARCH (β) and GARCH (σ) derive positive estimations that are statistically meaningful at the 1% level. We may claim that the conditional variance of both sukuk and the stock market is sensitive to prior shocks, and their volatility is persistent and varies gradually over time.

Additionally, the volatility of sukuk has been proven to be primarily driven by the estimated variance (GARCH term) rather than past shocks or news (ARCH term), which is consistent with Rahman et al. (2013). This result suggests that any news will significantly affect the price variation of both the sukuk and stock markets of the Dubai financial market and will take some time before the prices gradually return to balance.

Figure 7: Returns of Sukuk and Stocks

Source: Thomson Reuters

The volatility of the Dubai stock market can be attributed to the Dubai debt crisis. In fact, the

government borrowed 80 billion dollars in a very short delay (four years) to overcome the incredible challenge of being the new global hub for tourism and real estate investments. However, this incredible contest was not without consequences. The Dubai real estate sector suffered from a high property depression on a global scale, and without any surprise, this event severely impacted the stock market.

The *Figure 3* below illustrates the correlation between sukuk and stock returns. This correlation fluctuates over time, with a range of -1 to +0.95. This correlation was positive for most of the study, indicating that sukuk and stocks moved in the same direction most of the time, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic. However, the result reveals a strictly negative correlation of -1 during the Dubai debt crisis period. This remarkable observation highlights the distinct impact of the debt/financial crisis and the global pandemic on the dynamic correlation between sukuk and stocks. Therefore, Dubai's financial market investors should consider the external environment and uncertainty factors that significantly influence the financial market before formulating their portfolio allocation strategy.

Figure 8: Correlation (Sukuk-r and stock_r)

Source: Thomson Reuters

3.3. Granger Causality and impulse response function

To avoid any spurious regression analysis, we identify the existence of a cointegration between our variables. First, we estimated a VAR equation to select the adequate lag length for our model; based on our output and Akaike information criterion (Appendix 1), we chose 12 lag lengths and hence, we could run the Johansen cointegration analysis, the results of which are shown in *Table 3*.

Table 10: Johansen test

Hypothesized	Eigenvalue	Trace statistics	Probabilities
None	0.076750	451.3497	0.0000
At most one	0.065587	207.3106	0.0000

Source: Authors' own.

The co-integration (trace test) results in *Table 3* imply a co-integrating equation at the 0.05 level. Hence, there is a long-term equilibrium relationship between the Sukuk and stock markets in the Dubai financial market. Based on the cointegration test results, we had to estimate a vector error correction model (VECM) based on the cointegration test results and then run the Granger causality

and impulse response functions.

Granger argues that causality is defined based on two main assumptions: Firstly, the cause occurs before the effect. Secondly, the cause has unique information about the future value of its effect (Granger, 1980). Starting with these assumptions and referring to our causality test results (Appendix 2), we observe probabilities that we reject the null hypothesis and that a causality relationship exists in two directions. This suggests that higher sukuk returns lead to higher stock returns and vice versa.

Furthermore, the impulse response function figures (Appendix 3) demonstrate that both stocks and sukuk returns respond to their news, albeit with distinct reactions to each other. On the one hand, stock returns significantly influence sukuk returns, revealing a slight but positive and significant reaction to stock shocks. On the other hand, stock returns exhibit a strong positive reaction to the news about sukuk returns. The results from the impulse response functions add robustness to both the GRANGER and BEKK-GARCH results.

4. RESULTS AND IMPLICATIONS

Both sukuk and stock market indices are influenced by their respective news and exhibit volatility constancy across the study period. The environmental situation of the Dubai financial market advocates that the variation and sensitivity of researched equities are connected to the market's nature as a fast-growing emerging market, but not only the financial and political event changes have a significant impact on the financial market's behavior as well, with Dubai's financial debt as the primary cause of the market crash.

The correlation analysis between sukuk and stock returns shows a positive linkage between both assets, which means that the two properties are expected to move in the same direction for most of the study period, which supports the argument that sukuk are hybrid instruments from a structural point of view and have some similarities to stocks, which is coherent with Scip et al. (2016). Moreover, the bi-directional causality relationship between sukuk and stocks proves that both assets mutually influence each other and can help predict each other's future behavior.

For Muslim or other non-Muslim investors who have been out of the financial market due to their beliefs and moral orientations, Islamic financial tools such as Islamic stocks or the more famous Islamic Sukuk are supposed to be “the” perfect alternative to the conventional tools available in the market. Such tools are supposed to bring the missed “embeddedness” to the real economy, therefore backing the development and enhancement of the economy, which is coherent with the aspirations of the Islamic economic paradigm, and therefore contributing to a bigger goal, which is empowering the Muslim community and supporting a human-centric framework where the financial system is a tool to link finance to economic development. Indeed, *Figure 2* strongly supports this argument and shows similar trends in sukuk and stock returns.

Further, the macroeconomic environment of the Dubai financial market has a non-negligible impact on the dynamic linkage between sukuk and stocks. Indeed, previous research has proved that macroeconomic variables influence the dynamic co-movement and interdependency relations between stocks and sukuku. Piljak (2013) discovered that macroeconomic factors, particularly inflation, are crucial in explaining the stock-bond connection. Inflation, he said, is a vital driver of the stock-sukuk link. When there is much inflation, the cash-flow expectations result in a positive connection between the two asset classes. Additionally, during times of crisis, we can notice a lower correlation between sukuk and stocks, which is consistent with the reviewed literature.

The current Shariah-compliance stock climate includes specific concessions from a Shari'ah

compliance perspective. For instance, disclosing the impermissible elements is a crucial step in ensuring the continuity of the efficient operations of the markets, considering that the tolerance limits in the screening processes are tailored to a particular market need. With that in mind, the evidence shows that the variations in Shari'ah screening processes at times made a negative impact on the sukuk market regarding the level of market confidence (Htay et al., 2013), as well as in the specific matters of portfolio diversification (Zaidi et al., 2013). Therefore, standardization in Shari'ah screening processes is of utmost importance, and following AAOIFI and IFSB standards would ensure the unification of the process across the board.

5. CONCLUSION

This study uses many statistical tests, such as a bivariate BEKK-GARCH (1,1) model, Granger causality, and impulse response functions, to examine the shocks and volatility persistence of both sukuk and stocks. We also look at the causality link between the two, using daily prices from the Dubai Islamic Capital Market (Sukuk Index) and the conventional stock market (DFM index).

Our main findings are that the conditional variance of both sukuk and the stock market is sensitive to prior shocks, and their volatility is persistent and varies gradually over time.

Rahman et al. (2013) confirm that the estimate variance (GARCH term) primarily drives the volatility of sukuk, not past shocks or news (ARCH term). This result suggests that any innovation will have a meaningful effect on the price variation of both the sukuk and stock markets of the Dubai financial market and that it will take some time before the prices gradually return to Our study reveals a positive correlation between sukuk and stocks, likely due to their hybrid nature and similarities; however, we have observed a decrease in this correlation during the debt crisis.t crisis.

This study holds significance as it aims to provide investors in the Dubai financial market with significant results for their portfolio allocation strategy. Investors should not rely on sukuk as a safe haven for diversification purposes in times of crisis. The results show a strong interdependence between sukuk and stocks and bi-directional causality.

Stakeholders in the Islamic financial system, such as Shari'ah boards and regulators, are likely to benefit from the results of this study. The findings can potentially add value to further scholarly discussions and serve as a platform for a better understanding of the Islamic capital markets, particularly sukuk. The paper also sheds light on the critical Shari'ah-compliance screening element in the context of sukuk.

Future researchers could provide more evidence by identifying the time dependence relationship, using more statistical approaches such as wavelet analysis to enhance the robustness of both the Granger and M-GARCH models, and identifying the significant external macro-political factors influencing this correlation.

Declarations

The author has no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose. The data are available upon a reasonable request from the author.

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APPENDIX A1

Var Lag order Selection Criteria

Endogenous variables: R ST R SU

Exogenous variables: C

Included observations: 3049

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	20307.66	NA	5.63e-09	-13.31955	-13.31560	-13.31813
1	20353.33	91.226538	5.48e-09	-13.34689	-13.33504*	-13.34263
2	20357.84	8.990803	5.48e-09	-13.34722	-13.32747	-13.34012
3	20364.25	12.79011	5.47e-09	-13.34880	-13.32115	-13.33886
4	20365.70	2.895022	5.48e-09	-13.34713	-13.31157	-13.33435
5	20372.46	13.48250	5.47e-09	-13.34894	-13.30549	-13.33333
6	20376.11	7.263172	5.47e-09	-13.34871	-13.29763	-13.33025
7	20379.04	5.836412	5.47e-09	-13.34801	-13.28875	-13.32671
8	20385.59	13.02519	5.46e-09	-13.34968	-13.28253	-13.32555
9	20387.73	4.249980	5.47e-09	-13.34846	-13.27340	-13.32149
10	20396.40	17.22526	5.45e-09	-13.35153	-13.26857	-13.32171
11	20399.69	6.522607	5.45e-09	-13.35106	-13.26020	-13.31840
12	20404.60	9.744367*	5.45e-09	-13.35166*	-13.25289	-13.31616
13	20407.92	6.573582	5.45e-09	-13.35121	-13.24455	-13.31287
14	20409.72	3.574629	5.46e-09	-13.34977	-13.23520	-13.30859
15	20412.34	5.173860	5.47e-09	-13.34886	-13.22639	-13.30485
16	20415.76	6.781172	5.47e-09	-13.34848	-13.21812	-13.30163
17	20417.11	2.667001	5.48e-09	-13.34675	-13.20848	-13.29705
18	20420.05	5.806283	5.48e-09	-13.34605	-13.19988	-13.29352
19	20422.31	4.467398	5.49e-09	-13.34491	-13.19084	-13.28954
20	20423.77	2.872679	5.50e-09	-13.34324	-13.18127	-13.28503

*indicates lag order select by the criterion

LR: sequential modified LR test statistic (each test at 5% level)

FPE: Final prediction error

AIC: Akaike information criterion

SC: Schwarz information criterion

HQ: Hannan-Quinn information criterion

Source: Authors' own.

APPENDIX A2

VEC Granger Causality/Block Exogeneity Wald Tests
 Included observations: 3049

<i>Dependant variable D(R ST)</i>			
Excluded	Chi-sq	df	Prob.
D(R SU)	40.68712	12	0.0001
All	40.66712	12	0.0001

<i>Dependant variable D(R SU)</i>			
Excluded	Chi-sq	df	Prob.
D(R ST)	49.90588	12	0.0000
All	49.90588	12	0.0000

Source: Authors' own.

APPENDIX A3

Response to Cholesky One S.D. (d.f. adjusted) Innovations

Source: Authors' own.

A3. Abbreviations:

- AAOIFI: Accounting and Auditing Organization of Islamic Financial Institutions.
- ISFB: Islamic financial board.
- IIFM: International Islamic financial market
- IME: Islamic moral economy

